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A combined chemical and ecotoxicological approach to asses Nature-based Solutions efficiency in removing pharmaceuticals using microcosms.

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Abstract:	<p>Pharmaceutical products (PP) are considered contaminants of emerging concern, and their discharge into the environment has increased due to both, human and veterinary use. These drugs entered freshwater ecosystems and remain physiologically active, posing potential negative effects on aquatic ecosystems. As conventional plants for wastewater treatment are not designed to remove most of these micropollutants, the development of strategies for sustainable management is essential and nature-based solutions (NBS) will be useful in removing pollution, simultaneously benefiting people and nature. This study aims to assess the effectiveness of PP removal of different NBSs implemented at a microcosm scale from chemical and ecotoxicological points of view. Proposed NBSs were based on floating wetlands with improvements based on the use of biochar and bioaugmentation (biofilm coating). The proposed NBSs were able to reduce up to 90% of the total PP concentration after the whole experimental period (42 days). However, considering a regular hydraulic retention time (7 days), the higher PP removal rate (55%), took place in the microcosms with floating wetlands enhanced with biochar (FWB), followed by the floating wetlands enhanced with biofilm-coated biochar (FWBB) (51%) and the floating wetland (FW) (42%). The selected NBS (FWB) has also been assessed through the toxicological approach, and the acute and behavioural effects of the wastewater were also reduced after 7 days. The proposed solution will benefit both nature and society, reducing PP pollution and enhancing water resource quality. The results obtained with the ecotoxicological approach highlight the relevance of considering the toxic cocktail, as a whole, in environmental risk assessment and the use of behavioural biomarkers for spotlighting its ecological consequences.</p>
Response to Reviewers:	<p>Dear Editor,</p> <p>Thanks for your feedback on our manuscript "A combined chemical and ecotoxicological approach to asses Nature-based Solutions efficiency in removing pharmaceutical using microcosms" (by RODRÍGUEZ SANTAMARINA M., GILBERT LÓPEZ B., MARTÍNEZ-PIERNAS A.B.; MUÑOZ-COBO A.J., LÓPEZ-VALCARCEL M. E., JIMÉNEZ-MELERO R & G. PARRA.</p> <p>We have included all the suggested changes (Highlighted) in the text and the figures. In summary</p>

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Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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1 **A combined chemical and ecotoxicological approach to asses Nature-based**
2 **Solutions efficiency in removing pharmaceuticals using microcosms.**

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25
26 **ABSTRACT**

27 Pharmaceutical products (PP) are considered contaminants of emerging concern, and
28 their discharge into the environment has increased due to both, human and veterinary use.
29 These drugs entered freshwater ecosystems and remain physiologically active, posing
30 potential negative effects on aquatic ecosystems. As conventional plants for wastewater
31 treatment are not designed to remove most of these micropollutants, the development of
32 strategies for sustainable management is essential and nature-based solutions (NBS) will
33 be useful in removing pollution, simultaneously benefiting people and nature. This study
34 aims to assess the effectiveness of PP removal of different NBSs implemented at a

35 microcosm scale from chemical and ecotoxicological points of view. Proposed NBSs
36 were based on floating wetlands with improvements based on the use of biochar and
37 bioaugmentation (biofilm coating). The proposed NBSs were able to reduce up to 90%
38 of the total PP concentration after the whole experimental period (42 days). However,
39 considering a regular hydraulic retention time (7 days), the higher PP removal rate (55%),
40 took place in the microcosms with floating wetlands enhanced with biochar (FWB),
41 followed by the floating wetlands enhanced with biofilm-coated biochar (FWBB) (51%)
42 and the floating wetland (FW) (42%). The selected NBS (FWB) has also been assessed
43 through the toxicological approach, and the acute and behavioural effects of the
44 wastewater were also reduced after 7 days. The proposed solution will benefit both nature
45 and society, reducing PP pollution and enhancing water resource quality. The results
46 obtained with the ecotoxicological approach highlight the relevance of considering the
47 toxic cocktail, as a whole, in environmental risk assessment and the use of behavioural
48 biomarkers for spotlighting its ecological consequences.

49

50 **1. Introduction**

51

52 In 2009, Rockström et al. presented the conceptual framework of planetary boundaries
53 that defines a series of thresholds to achieve the stability of the Earth [1]. One of these
54 boundaries is the contamination by novel entities or contaminants of emerging concern
55 (CECs). The term was defined by [2], which encompasses chemicals, such as drugs, and
56 other new types of engineered materials or organisms not previously known to the Earth
57 system, as well as natural elements, for example, heavy metals, mobilized by
58 anthropogenic activities and accumulated at high concentrations. These toxic substances
59 reach freshwater and marine ecosystems, likely affecting aquatic organisms, potentially
60 causing alterations in trophic webs, and affecting ecosystems functioning and stability
61 [3]. In addition, likely this pollution will intensify in the future, due to the increase in the
62 activity of the chemical industry over time [4].

63 PP are considered CECs and their discharge into the environment has increased due to
64 the human population increase and aging and their veterinary use [5]. These drugs that
65 have entered freshwater ecosystems remain physiologically active, disturbing the
66 ecosystems [6]. The number of studies on the toxic effects of PP that reach aquatic
67 environments has increased recently [7–9] highlighting the significant ecological and
68 health risks and the necessary research on effective mitigation strategies [10]. Therefore,

69 PPs have contributed significantly to aquatic pollution, with urban wastewater being one
70 of the largest pollution sources [11].

71 Conventional plants for wastewater treatment were not designed to remove most of
72 the CECs [11]. Additionally, until now, they have not been subjected to specific
73 regulations regarding their limit of presence in water, so there is no monitoring of these
74 compounds in the different environmental compartments (water, sediments, biota) [12].
75 However, the European Council recently adopts new rules for more efficient treatments,
76 and by 2045 member states will have to apply additional treatments to
77 remove micropollutants (such as pharmaceuticals and cosmetics), known as quaternary
78 treatment [13]. In this concern, developing strategies for sustainable water resources
79 management is essential. Given this, some studies have called for further monitoring
80 studies to better understand the impact on environmental contamination by
81 pharmaceuticals and to evaluate the necessity for quaternary treatments, such as the NBS
82 [14]. NBS are actions to protect, sustainably manage, and restore natural and modified
83 ecosystems that address societal challenges effectively and adaptively, simultaneously
84 benefiting people and nature [15]. Two of the key aspects in NBS are the integrity of the
85 ecosystem-society binomial, as well as the evident link with the Sustainable Development
86 Goals (SDGs), since it is not possible to understand the progress of society without
87 considering the preservation of the environment and the sustainability of natural resources
88 [16].

89 The aquatic plant community can purify water naturally, improving its quality. They
90 are based on the natural processes of biological filtering of water as it passes through
91 shallow areas and permeable soils. Emerging plants like cattails (*Thypha* sp.) absorb and
92 eliminate nutrients such as N and P. They can also decompose contaminants and toxins
93 from sediment and water by incorporating them into their biomass. But they also provide
94 shelter and surface to other organisms, such as microorganisms, plankton, and fish that
95 can help with the absorption of nutrients and the decomposition of pollutants that reach
96 the aquatic systems [17]. So, they can be considered NBS when used to remove pollution
97 from wastewater [18,19]. NBS designed to improve water quality, such as the artificial or
98 constructed wetlands, are tools that allow the sustainable use of water resources and the
99 protection of aquatic systems threatened by pollutants and whose effectiveness has been
100 verified in a wide variety of experiences and situations [20]. The use of the plants and
101 microorganisms' natural capacity to decompose pollutants through biological processes
102 is known as bioremediation and is part of the processes that classify NBS as amelioration

103 solutions (amelioration-NBS type, following [21]) and are considered a low-cost and
104 environmentally friendly option [22]. The use of artificial or constructed wetlands as
105 NBS, specifically floating wetlands, has been previously reported as an efficient strategy
106 to eliminate pollutants [23]. For example, a floating treatment wetland (FTW) was used
107 as a strategy for attenuating the pollutant concentration in a crude oil wastewater pit,
108 being successful in removing organics, hydrocarbons, total dissolved solids, and heavy
109 metals [24].

110 To improve the PP removal capacity of artificial wetlands, we can incorporate
111 adsorbent elements, such as biochar, a carbon-rich material that can be prepared from
112 various organic waste feedstocks, such as agricultural plant residues and sewage sludge
113 [25]. It has been demonstrated that biochar prepared from olive oil wastes eliminated
114 emerging contaminants from water at laboratory scale [26]. The PP elimination yields
115 vary according to the PP typology between 40-96%. The properties of these materials
116 (physical, chemical, and biological) make them optimal for wastewater decontamination
117 treatments [27] [28][29–31]. El Barkaoui and collaborators reviewed the use of Biochar
118 in constructed wetlands in the literature and stated that the removal efficiency of
119 pollutants in constructed wetlands is affected by several factors, such as substrate
120 chemical and physical properties, oxygenation, and hydraulic retention time, among
121 others [31]. The use of biochar as an innovative amendment can enhance the removal
122 efficiencies of nitrogen, emerging organic contaminants, and metals in constructed
123 wetlands treatment systems, simultaneously mitigating the greenhouse effect and
124 reducing the land requirement of these nature-based solutions [28].

125 Another removal enhancement strategy is based on using specific microorganisms
126 capable of reducing PP. These organisms can be found in ecosystems with a history of
127 pollution by PP [32] and they have been used in bioaugmentation lab experiments [33].
128 Although it is a little-studied field, some authors have studied the interactions between
129 biochars and microbial biofilms, analysing the potential advantages and disadvantages of
130 this association in the elimination of some types of contaminants [34,35]. For example, a
131 study also confirmed that FTWs inoculated with bacteria possessed hydrocarbon
132 degradation capability [36]. The role of the presence of strong increases in polar
133 functional groups associated with stable biofilms in pharmaceutical contaminant
134 purification systems still presents important unknowns that are partly intended to be
135 analysed in this work. These functional groups are also present in microbial biomass and
136 other authors have that these chemical groups are involved in the adsorption of

137 pharmaceutical and personal care products [37]. On the other hand, conventional biochar
138 obtained by simple carbonization usually has low porosity, which limits its adsorption
139 capacity, while their chemical activation is expensive [38]. For this reason, we aimed to
140 assess if biochar enhanced with microbial biofilm could improve its adsorption capacity
141 against pharmaceuticals.

142 We hypothesised that both strategies, the use of biochar and the use of biofilm-coated
143 biochar, enhance the floating wetland capacity of removing PP, and reduce the toxic effect
144 from wastewater, functioning as innovative NBSs.

145 This study aims to assess the effectiveness of PP removal of the different NBSs
146 implemented at microcosms scale, firstly from a chemical point of view analysing the
147 rate of PP removal; and secondly, from an ecotoxicological point of view, analysing the
148 toxicity of the wastewater, before and after the NBS, using standard and innovative
149 toxicological protocols. The combination of both assessments is key to informing
150 quantitatively and qualitatively on the NBSs' efficiency.

151

152

153 **2. Material and methods**

154

155 *2.1. Chemicals and reagents*

156

157 A total of 107 pharmaceuticals and some of their relevant transformation products
158 were included in the monitoring (Table S1). The selection of the analytes was based on
159 those commonly found in wastewater effluents from the area [39] as well as some
160 compounds included in the European Watch List published by the European Parliament
161 in 2022. Analytical standards (purity \geq 98%) were purchased from Dr. Ehrenstorfer
162 (Augsburg, Germany) and Merck Group (Darmstadt, Germany). A surrogate standard
163 solution of difenoxuron in methanol (MeOH) was used as an internal standard (IS) for
164 extraction quality control check. Acetonitrile (ACN), MeOH, and water (LC-MS grade)
165 were acquired from Merck Group (Darmstadt, Germany). Formic acid (FA) was supplied
166 by Honeywell Fluka (Buchs, Switzerland). Oasis HLB SPE cartridges (200 mg, 6 mL)
167 were acquired from Waters (Milford, MA, USA).

168

169 *2.2. Biochar characterization*

170

171 The ground biochar used in the study is generated from pruning biomass using the
172 hydrothermal carbonization process and it was provided by INGELIA S.L. The company
173 provides also the general characterization of moisture (7%), ash content (5-10% dry
174 weight), total carbon (55-60 % ash-free dry weight-AFDW), total nitrogen (1-1.5%
175 AFDW), volatiles (45-55 % on carbon) and lower heating value (LHV 22-23 MJ/kg). The
176 biochar bulk or apparent density is 750 kg m⁻³.

177

178 2.3 Biofilm-coated biochar process

179

180 A ubiquitous strain isolated from wastewater from the province of Jaén [40] and
181 registered in the Spanish collection of type cultures (CECT) was selected to evaluate its
182 ability to form biofilms that improve the adsorption capacity of PP by the pruning biochar
183 pellets chosen for this work. *Rhodotorula mucilaginosa* 1S1 CECT 13212 had already
184 shown a good biosorption capacity for Ag(I) [41] based on a strong presence of hydroxyl,
185 carbonyl, amino, methyl, and methylene functional groups, which suggested that it could
186 provide an improvement in the adsorption of the organic molecules evaluated in this
187 research. Using Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FT-IR) we analysed whether
188 biochar enhanced with microbial biofilm could improve its adsorption capacity against
189 PP. Before starting the tests, the pellets were subjected to light sterilization at 85 °C for
190 48 h. Starting with a 24-h pre-inoculum on YPG medium (yeast, 10 g L⁻¹; peptone, 10 g
191 L⁻¹; glucose, 20 g L⁻¹), batch tests were started at 27 °C and 150 rpm. The biochar was
192 placed in a sterile mesh to prevent damage from the agitation conditions. After 10 days
193 of growth, the pellets were washed repeatedly with 0.1 M NaCl and under shaking
194 conditions to remove any remains of the nutrient medium. Finally, samples were taken
195 and fixed with 2.5% glutaraldehyde, they were dehydrated with increasing concentrations
196 of acetone and after drying at 35 °C, they were metalized with carbon for analysis by
197 scanning electron microscopy (SEM) with the idea of confirming the colonization of the
198 microorganism on the surface of the biochar. In parallel, an analysis of FT-IR by
199 attenuated total refraction (ATR) was carried out on the biochar pellets previously ground
200 in porcelain mortar (before and after growing biofilm), to check the presence of functional
201 groups. Both, biochar and biofilm-coated biochar, were used in batch tests to determine
202 the adsorption of carbamazepine, diclofenac, and sulfamethoxazole under laboratory
203 conditions (Table S2) and analysed by FT-IR. Both materials were later used in the
204 microcosm-scale experiment framed in the NBS proposed in this work.

205

206 *2.4 Microcosms setup and stabilization phase*

207

208 Twenty polypropylene containers (556 x 356 x 304 mm) were used as microcosms.
209 They were placed in the experimental wetland, an area at the University of Jaén (Spain)
210 devoted to research under outdoor conditions. They were filled with previously
211 dechlorinated tap water, reaching a final volume of 30 L. Floating wetlands were
212 assembled following the supplier instructions with 6 plants of *Thypha* sp. species inserted
213 in the plastic tile in each microcosm (QUARQ ENTERPRISE S.A.) (Microcosms'
214 pictures in Supplementary material **Fig. S1**). The microcosms were stabilized for 5 weeks,
215 allowing the plants to develop before wastewater exposure. Microcosms were monitored
216 weekly, using the YSI-556MPS multiparametric probe to measure: temperature (°C), pH,
217 conductivity (mS/cm), and dissolved oxygen (%). Aquaflor fluorometer (Turner Designs)
218 was used to measure chlorophyll-*a* content (Chl-*a*).

219

220 *2.5. Microcosms wastewater exposure phase*

221

222 After 5 weeks of stabilization, the microcosms were exposed to wastewater (WW)
223 from the Santa Catalina Wastewater Treatment Plant (secondary treatment, Jaén, Spain).
224 Static systems were used in this study. The treatments studied were as follows. **Null**
225 **treatment**: microcosms without floating wetland, with WW; **Control FW**: microcosms
226 with floating wetland with stabilization phase water; **FW**: microcosms with floating
227 wetland with WW; **FWB**: microcosms with floating wetland with WW, improved with
228 biochar; **FWBB**: microcosms with floating wetland with WW, improved with biofilm
229 coated biochar. Four replicates for each treatment were established.

230

231 In those treatments with biochar, the microcosms received 60 g of biochar distributed
232 in 6 permeable bags located close to the *Thypha* sp. radicular section (**Fig. S1**). The
233 exposure phase lasted 7 weeks, and samples were taken every 3 days during the first
234 week, and then once per week until the end of the study: days 0, 3, 7, 14, 21, 28, 35, and
235 42. The chemical, physical, and biological parameters mentioned in the stabilization
236 phase were also measured on each sampling day during the exposure phase. Further, water
237 samples were taken from each microcosm for subsequent semiquantitative nutrient
238 analysis (nitrate, using the VISOCOLOR™ ECO Rapid Kits; Phosphate content using
QUANTOFIX™ Quick Strips. Additionally, samples were taken in 1 L amber glass

239 bottles from each microcosm to carry out the analysis of pharmaceuticals by liquid
240 chromatography/mass spectrometry (LC-MS). The bottles were filled with a syringe to a
241 volume of 750 mL and closed with Teflon caps. After that, the bottles were superficially
242 disinfected with ethanol, labelled, and finally frozen at -20 °C until analysed.

243

244 *2.6 Monitoring of pharmaceuticals*

245 *2.6.1 Sample preparation*

246 Samples were defrosted and filtered (cellulose, 0.45 µm pore size). A solid-phase
247 extraction (SPE) procedure, based on our previous studies [39] [42] was applied. Briefly,
248 200 mL of treated water were spiked with an IS solution and extracted using an Oasis
249 HLB cartridge. The SPE cartridge was preconditioned with 4 mL of MeOH and 8 mL of
250 H₂O (LC-MS grade). After sample loading, the cartridge was dried under vacuum for
251 30 min. The elution of the analytes was performed with two aliquots of 4 mL of MeOH.
252 The extract was then evaporated in a water bath (37 °C) under a gentle nitrogen stream
253 (15 psi) until dryness (30 min approx.), and reconstituted with 2 mL of MeOH. Before
254 injection in the LC-MS, a 1:50 dilution of the extract using Milli-Q water was carried out.
255 Therefore, the complete procedure involves a global 2:1 preconcentration of the WW
256 sample [42].

257

258 *2.6.2 Sample analysis by LC-MS and Quantification*

259

260 Instrumental analysis was carried out using the same conditions as previously reported
261 [42]. A Thermo Vanquish Flex LC system (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA,
262 USA) coupled with a Q-Exactive Orbitrap (Thermo Fisher Scientific) mass spectrometer
263 was employed for sample analysis. A Zorbax Rapid Resolution High Definition (RRHD)
264 Eclipse Plus C18 (2.1 mm × 50 mm, 1.8 µm, Agilent Technologies, Wilmington, DE,
265 USA) analytical column was used for chromatographic separation. A mixture of ultrapure
266 water (0.1% FA, eluent A) and MeOH (0.1% FA, eluent B) was used as the mobile phase.
267 The gradient employed was as follows: initial conditions, 10% B for 0.7 min; within 4.0
268 min, linear increase from 10% to 50%; within 17 min, linear increase to 95% B; kept
269 constant at 95% B for 8 min; within 0.1 min decreased to 10% B; and kept constant for
270 column equilibration during 5 min. The total analysis run time was 30 min.

271 The mass spectrometer was equipped with a heated electrospray ionization source
272 (HESI) operating in both positive and negative modes (individual analysis). The HESI

273 parameters were as follows: sheath gas flow rate 55 units; aux gas flow rate 15 units;
274 spray voltage 3.5 kV (2.5 kV, negative ionization); capillary temperature 300 °C; S-lens
275 RF level 60; and aux gas heater temperature 350 °C. The detection of the compounds was
276 performed using a combination of full-scan (FS) and data-dependent acquisition (DDA)
277 for MS/MS spectra. For FS analysis, data were acquired at a resolving power of 70,000
278 FWHM; the automatic gain control (AGC) target was set at 3×10^6 with a maximum
279 injection time (IT) of 100 ms, and a scan range from m/z 65 to 950. For DDA, resolution
280 was 17,500 FWHM; AGC target 2×10^5 ; Maximum IT 100 ms; loop count 5; maximum
281 number of ions to trigger after FS based on ion abundance (TopN) 5; isolation window 1
282 Da; and normalized collision energy (NCE) set at 35. Xcalibur 3.0 and Trace Finder 3.3
283 (Thermo Fisher Scientific) software were used for qualitative and quantitative data
284 analysis.

285 The methodology was validated by assessing linearity, method quantification limits
286 (MQLs), matrix effects, trueness (expressed as recoveries), and precision (expressed as
287 relative standard deviations, RSDs). Detailed validation results for the 107 compounds
288 studied can be found elsewhere [42]. For quantification purposes, the concentration of
289 the PP was calculated by interpolating the obtained peak area in matrix-matched
290 calibration curves (range 0.005 – 5 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$).

291

292

293 2.7. Toxicological assessment

294

295 Two toxicological tests were carried out using *Daphnia magna* as the test organism to
296 evaluate the environmental risk that wastewater PP cocktails may pose to aquatic biota.

297 Firstly, an acute toxicity test based on the OECD protocol [43] was carried out to find
298 the wastewater LD50 (lethal dilution) for the *D. magna* population cultured at the
299 University of Jaén. *D. magna* was reared in mineral water in the laboratory for many
300 years using the microalga *Scenedesmus obliquus* (Turpin) Kützing 1833 as food
301 (Chemical Engineering Laboratory, University of Jaén). These algae were routinely
302 maintained in 3 N-BBM*V culture media at pH 8.3–8.5 (modified from CCAP, Scotland).
303 Both, *D. magna* and *S. obliquus* were cultured in a temperature-controlled chamber
304 (ARALAB-600PHL-LED) and under the same conditions (20 °C and a 12:12 h light:dark
305 cycle). Enriched mineral water (EMW) with thiamine (0.075 g L⁻¹), vitamin B12 (0.010
306 g L⁻¹), biotin (0.0075 g L⁻¹), and sodium selenite (0.010 g L⁻¹) was used following Díaz-

307 Báez et al (2008) culture protocol. WW from the Santa Catalina wastewater treatment
308 plant effluent (WWTP) was used to prepare the treatments for the acute toxicity test:
309 Control treatment (100% EMW used for daphnids culture, also used to make the
310 dilutions); 25% WW treatment (25% WW + 75% EMW); 50% WW treatment (50% WW
311 + 50% EMW); 75% WW treatment (75% WW + 25% EMW), and 100% WW treatment
312 (100% WW). Ten daphnids (<24 h) were added to each replicate (3 replicates in each
313 treatment). Therefore, 150 individuals were used and maintained under the same culture
314 conditions of light and temperature (ARALAB-600PHL-LED chamber) but without food.
315 Survival was checked after 24 hours and 48 hours.

316 Secondly, two avoidance behaviour tests were conducted to assess the effects on *D.*
317 *magna* behaviour. In the first one, we use the WW, and in the second one, we use the
318 water from FWB microcosms taken by the end of the exposure period (day 42). We
319 decided to use the FWB treatment as representative of the innovative NBSs proposed,
320 and due to the limitation of only being able to perform an HeMHAS experiment. We have
321 followed the methodology used by Moreira & collaborators [44] and the HeMHAS
322 system (Heterogeneous Multi-Habitat Assay System). This system allows a non-forced
323 exposure to toxicants and the analysis of the avoidance or escape behaviour, when the
324 individuals select the most convenient/safe compartment. In the first test, the dilutions set
325 was: i) 100% *D. magna* culture water (EMW), ii) 50% wastewater from the treatment
326 plant (WW) + 50% EMW, and iii) 100% WW. In the second test, carried out to confirm
327 the effect of the water from the FWB, the dilutions set was: i) 100% EMW, ii) 50% water
328 from microcosms FWB + 50% EMW and iii) 100% water from microcosms FWB (**Fig.**
329 **1**). Ten adult daphnids were placed in each compartment, with the gates open allowing
330 the movement of individuals along the dilution gradient. Individuals in each compartment
331 were counted every half hour until reaching 4 hours. The last check was carried out after
332 24 hours. HeMHAS system allows to perform 3 replicates per trial, using 150 individuals
333 on the whole.

334

335 2.8 Statistical analysis

336

337 The microcosm stabilization period results were analyzed with a Generalized linear
338 model (GLM) and Tukey post hoc to test differences among microcosm concerning the
339 measured variables (physicochemical and biological variables). RStudio software was
340 used.

341 A shade chart was plotted to visualize the concentration patterns of PP on the different
342 treatments over time. A non-metric multidimensional scaling (nMDS) ordination plot,
343 based on the Bray-Curtis similarities among treatments, was carried out; the closer points
344 are to each other the more similar the PP composition of the different NBSs [45]. Success
345 of the ordination was measured by a stress coefficient [46].

346 To detect differences in PP composition between treatments over time, a multivariate
347 analysis of the PP data was performed using a Permutational Analysis of Variance
348 (PERMANOVA). A two-way design was implemented, that is, the factor NBSs with 4
349 levels (Null; FW; FWB; FWBB), the factor time with 3 levels (0, 3 and 7 days) and the
350 interaction between them. This analysis was undertaken with 9999 permutations on Bray-
351 Curtis similarity matrices.

352 In addition, a Similarity Percentage Analyses (SIMPER) was performed to identify the
353 discriminant PPs between treatments (i.e., which PP contributes to the differences
354 between PP assemblages) [45]. PRIMER v7 software was used to perform all these
355 analyses. Data were previously fourth root transformed in order to reduce the influence
356 of more abundant PP and increase the influence of rarer PP in the analysis [46].

357 Several two-way Generalized Linear Model (GLM), with Poisson distribution and log-
358 link function, were performed [47] to detect the potential effects of NBSs and time and
359 their interaction on the abundances of PP.

360 Acute toxicity test results were analysed using the non-parametric test Kruskal-Wallis
361 test to evaluate differences among treatments (non-normal distributed data). To perform
362 multiple comparisons between groups, the Dunn test with Holm adjustment was applied.

363 Avoidance behaviour test results were analysed using analysis of variance (ANOVA)
364 to assess differences in means among treatments (normal distributed data). To further
365 investigate which specific groups were different, a Tukey Honest Significant Difference
366 (HSD) test was conducted

367

368 **3. Results**

369

370 *3.1. Biofilm-coated biochar process*

371

372 The preliminary results obtained in the biological activation tests of the biochar
373 demonstrated that the yeast *R. mucilaginosa* 1S1 CECT 13212 had a good capacity to

374 promote biofilm formation on the mentioned organic support (**Fig. S2**), showing a strong
375 release of exopolysaccharides (EPS) by the yeast and a uniform distribution.

376 On the other hand, the FT-IR spectra obtained before and after the formation of
377 microbial biofilm showed a slight increase in the intensity of the functional groups
378 concerning the original biochar with a predominance of hydroxyl groups associated with
379 two regions with intervals located at 3000-3300 cm^{-1} and at 900-1200 cm^{-1} ; methyl (CH_3)
380 and methylene (CH_2) groups derived from C-H bonds in the regions between 3000-2800
381 cm^{-1} and 1300-1500 cm^{-1} ; carbonyl ($\text{C}=\text{O}$) and amino (NH) groups associated with
382 amides I and II in the region between 1500 and 1800 cm^{-1} ; and phosphate groups (P-O)
383 represented in the bands in the region located between 900 and 1300 cm^{-1} .

384 Table S2 shows the results obtained in the batch adsorption tests and it was observed
385 that the biochar associated with microbial biofilm had improved the adsorption in the case
386 of diclofenac while the other two compounds have been absorbed slightly worse. In
387 general, the batch adsorption stage caused significant changes in the FTIR spectra (**Fig.**
388 **S3**), including changes in intensity and shifts in the bands. The bands located between
389 1300 and 600 cm^{-1} underwent significant changes, and this shows that the groups
390 associated with this region were involved in the adsorption of the pharmaceutical
391 compounds studied.

392 These results allow us to confirm that the biochar alone presented a wide range of
393 functional groups that can interact with the PP. Likewise, *R. mucilaginosa* 1S1 CECT
394 13212 and the microbial biofilm created have also been shown to increase the number of
395 functional groups, leading to a potential increase in PP biosorption capacity by the
396 biochar.

397

398 *3.2. Microcosms stabilization phase and wastewater exposure phase*

399

400 During the stabilization phase, the microcosm showed similar values in the physic-
401 chemical and biological variables, allowing the macrophyte stabilization and growth
402 (mean \pm SD, Temperature: 23.98 ± 0.85 °C; D.O.: 69.39 ± 2.55 %; pH: 5.83 ± 0.25 ;
403 Conductivity: 0.92 ± 0.07 mS/cm; and Chlorophyll *a*: 48.56 ± 33.58 mg L^{-1}). Concerning
404 the exposure phase, at the end of this period (day 42), there were differences between the
405 Null treatment and the rest of the treatments just in pH (**Table S3**).

406

407 *3.3. Chemical assessment*

408

409 The wastewater (WW) samples were from the Jaén treatment plant (115,000
410 inhabitants). Nine compounds showed saturated signals in the LC-MS analysis (caffeine,
411 antipyrine, paracetamol, theobromine, theophylline, naproxen, valsartan, nicotine, and
412 cotinine). Therefore, they were discarded from the study due to the impossibility of
413 reinjecting diluted sample extracts for their proper quantification. Overall, a total of 39
414 active substances were quantified in WW samples: (2-ethylidene-1-5-dimethyl-3-3-
415 diphenyl-pyrrolidine perchlorate, 9(10h)-acridone, acridine, atenolol, bupropion,
416 carbamazepine, carbamazepine 10-11-epoxide, citalopram, clarithromycin, cocaine,
417 codeine, diclofenac, diphenhydramine, eprosartan, flecainide, fluconazole, flufenamic
418 acid, gabapentin, gemfibrozil, irbesartan, ketamine, ketoprofen, lamotrigine, lidocaine,
419 mepivacaine, metformin, methadone, morphine, N-methylephedrine, O-
420 desmethylvenlafaxine, sotalol, sulfamethoxazole, sulfapyridine, sulpiride, telmisartan,
421 timolol, tramadol, trimethoprim, and venlafaxine). Ten of these positive findings
422 corresponded to substances included in the Watch List for surface water monitoring [48]:
423 clarithromycin, diclofenac, clotrimazole, fluconazole, O-desmethylvenlafaxine,
424 venlafaxine, metformin, ciprofloxacin, sulfamethoxazole, and trimethoprim.

425 After the exposure period in those microcosms without any NBS (treatment Null), 4
426 pharmaceutical products were not detected after 3 days (2-ethylidene-1-5-dimethyl-3-3-
427 diphenyl-pyrrolidine, bupropion, citalopram and cocaine). These PP were not included in
428 the heat maps created for the whole experimental period (**Fig. 2**), where the colour
429 intensity was used to represent PP average concentration in each treatment. The data were
430 separated into two different concentration ranges, creating two heat maps for a better
431 visualization of the PP removal process (below and over 100 ng L⁻¹).

432 We decided to further analyse the changes in PP composition in the first 7 days of the
433 experiment as, under WWTP regular conditions, water flows in through the artificial
434 wetland with an average hydraulic retention time of around this lapse of time. Considering
435 the global PP concentration, the removal rate by day 7 indicates that those NBSs with
436 biochar showed higher efficiency. The higher PP removal rate took place in the
437 microcosms with FWB, followed by the FWBB, and significantly different from the FW
438 and Null treatment removal rates ($F_{(3,7)}=72.632; p < 0.001$; **Fig. 3**). The non-metric multi-
439 dimensional scaling (nMDS) ordination plot based on the Bray-Curtis similarities (Figure
440 4) shown a gradient in PP structure from day 0 to day 7 (along MDS axis 1) and related
441 to NBSs (along MDS axis 2). The 2-d stress level was low, 0.06, so this nMDS provides

442 an excellent representation in reduced dimensions. The PP composition of the FWB on
443 day 7 was different from the rest of the treatments on the same day and very different
444 from the PP composition at the beginning of the experiment. On day 3, the composition
445 of PP in FWB and FWBB were more similar to each other than to the rest of the
446 treatments.

447 Indeed, these results agreed with a two-way PERMANOVA which detected significant
448 differences in the PP composition between NBSs (Pseudo- $F_{(3,17)} = 25,88$; $p = 0.001$) and
449 a significant effect of the exposure time (Pseudo- $F_{(2,17)} = 153.06$; $p = 0.001$). The
450 interaction was also significant (Pseudo- $F_{(6,17)} = 6.784$; $p = 0.001$); in fact, as nMDS
451 shown, in all NBSs, PP composition changed over time, but these differences were less
452 noticeable for FWBB and more remarkable for FWB (**Fig. 4**).

453 Considering the individualized PP GLM results, the PP's concentrations were
454 significantly reduced by the treatments ($p < 0.05$), just Ketamine and Sulfapyridine
455 concentrations were not different among treatments ($\chi^2_{(3,20)} = 2.43$; $p = 0.4881$ and $\chi^2_{(3,20)}$
456 $= 4.6101$; $p = 0.2027$, respectively).

457 In **Table 1** the dissimilarity percentages values were presented, confirming that the
458 higher PP removal took place in the FWB microcosms, followed by the FWBB. To
459 elucidate which PPs contribute to the differentiation between treatments, a SIMPER was
460 performed. **Table 2** shows the discriminant PP among the wastewater treatment plant
461 (WWTP, day 0) and the treatments at day 7. To identify the PP that contributes the most
462 to the differentiation between groups, the focus should be on the Average Dissimilarity
463 column; they will also tend to be the PPs with the larger abundances. In addition, to detect
464 the best indicator of the differences between those groups, Diss/SD ratio should also be
465 considered, since it can sometimes indicate PP that are completely absent in one group
466 and with very consistent presence in the other, but with low abundance [45]. Checking
467 both indicators (i.e., Av. Diss. and Diss/SD), we observed that both treatments, FWB and
468 FWBB, were very effective in reducing or removing irbesartan, ketoprofen,
469 clarithromycin, diphenhydramine, and metformin, among others (**Table 2c-d**). However,
470 the SIMPER shows the discriminant PP among treatments in day 7 (**Table 3**), FWB
471 removed more efficiently codeine, flufenamic acid, sotalol, timolol and 9(10H)-acridone,
472 among others, than FWBB (**Table 3f**). All the NBS (FW, FWB, FWBB) were effective in
473 eliminating diphenhydramine and methadone in less than 3 days (**Fig. 2; Table 3**), while
474 both PP were still in the Null microcosms by that time. Both FWB and FWBB were

475 effective in removing completely in less than 3 days ibersartan and N-methilephedirne.
476 FWBB was effective in removing completely in less than 3 days clarithromycin (**Fig. 2**).

477

478 3.4. Toxicological assessment

479

480 3.4.1. Acute test

481

482 After 48 h *D. magna* exposed to wastewater showed lower survival than the control
483 (culture water). There was a 20% reduction in *D. magna* survival in those vessels with
484 100% WW (without dilution) compared to control vessels (culture water) (**Fig. 5**) ($\chi^2_{(4,15)} = 10.5; p = 0.0328$).

486

487 3.4.2. Avoidance behaviour tests

488

489 In the first avoidance behaviour test and after 24 hours of exposure, the number of
490 individuals in the compartments decreases as the dilution of WW decrease too, indicating
491 that individuals of *D. magna* are selecting compartments without WW, avoiding the
492 exposure to it (**Fig. 6a**; $F_{(4,10)} = 3.781; p = 0.0401$).

493 In the second avoidance behaviour test and after 24 hours of exposure, there were no
494 differences in the number of individuals among compartments, indicating that *D. magna*
495 individuals did not avoid the compartments with water from FWB microcosm, regardless
496 the dilution (**Fig. 6b**; $F_{(4,10)} = 2.009; p = 0.169$).

497

498 4. Discussion

499

500 Our results showed that the three proposed NBSs: FW, FWB and FWBB, enhanced
501 the PP removal from WW. However, the highest water quality improvement (higher PP
502 removal rate) was obtained with FWB treatment. This finding could be attributed to the
503 biochar adsorption capacity, which, as shown in Figure S2, has numerous active
504 functional groups.

505 The presence of the *R. mucilaginosa* 1S1 CECT 13212 in FWBB was also found to
506 have increased the PP removal but without differences compared to FWB. In general,
507 biological activation did not improve the adsorption capacity of the biochar, although, as

508 mentioned (section 3.3; caption Fig. S3), it seems to do so for some of the compounds,
509 such as tramadol, which usually involves the participation of O-H and C-O groups [49].

510 In general, the groups present in both the biochar and the biofilm involve the presence
511 of oxygen and nitrogen atoms. These atoms are also present in the molecules of the
512 compounds studied and this makes these molecules able to accept hydrogens while the
513 groups present in the adsorbent complex can donate hydrogens forming dipole-dipole
514 interactions known as hydrogen bonds [34]. Likewise, the fact proven in this work of the
515 presence of polar functional groups that have both positive and negative partial charges
516 indicates that the presence of electrostatic interactions may also be present in this case as
517 other authors have previously demonstrated [50][51]. The electrostatic interaction has a
518 strong dependence on the ionic strength of the medium but also on the pH, which in our
519 case remained slightly above neutrality and would therefore be facilitating this
520 mechanism by preventing the protonation of the functional groups allowing them to have
521 a negative charge [51]. Another mechanism that cannot be ruled out is the presence of
522 hydrophobic interactions, since non-polar groups tend to group, minimizing their contact
523 with water molecules. Finally, some authors have indicated that the pore filling of biochar
524 is also present among the bioremediation mechanisms of some pharmaceutical products
525 [34].

526 However, the lack of general improvement in the response of biofilm-coated biochar
527 might be explained by the heterogeneity of the plant matter used to manufacture the
528 biochars (state of vegetative maturity and nature of the plant residue) and also by the
529 heterogeneity of the resulting ground material [52]. The above could affect the particle
530 diameter or porosity, all of which could affect the final specific surface area and, therefore
531 the availability of the functional groups present in the biochar (biofilm-coated or not). At
532 the same time, this heterogeneity could affect biofilm formation by *R. mucilaginosa* 1S1,
533 so the coat may not have been uniform. Finally, all of this could mean that the
534 predominant factor in PP adsorption was the specific characteristics of the ground biochar
535 in each case, above the biological activation caused by the microbial biofilm. To what
536 extent it is interesting to biologically coat a biochar and quantify its final contribution to
537 PP adsorption should be studied more thoroughly in the future since the data suggest that
538 a longer activation over time can generate much more active and stable biofilms in real
539 conditions which can undoubtedly significantly increase the adsorption capacity of
540 organic molecules by biochar.

541 During the stabilization period (no exposure) all microcosms showed similar
542 environmental and biological variable values, which allows us to defend the experimental
543 design and initial conditions for the later exposure period. While, at the end of the
544 exposure to wastewater, the microcosms showed statistical differences just in pH, being
545 NULL microcosms which showed higher pH values. The other treatments with NBS
546 showed similar data. So, biochar and biofilm-coated biochar addition to floating wetlands
547 did not generate differences between NBS treatments, at least for the measured
548 environmental variables.

549 Several PP were removed in the microcosms with no NBS (Null treatment). This is
550 consistent with previous studies describing that some organic contaminants suffer
551 photodegradation through abiotic reactions under outdoor conditions [53,54].

552 Diverse PP removal efficiency was observed among treatments. Although PP
553 concentration decreased at all NBS microcosms, the FWB treatment was the most
554 effective. The chemical assessment allows us to select the most efficient treatment from
555 those proposed. The use of floating wetlands enhanced with biochar at a microcosms scale
556 and the confirmation of its PP removal capacity allows us to defend it to be used at a
557 larger scale. Several PP were completely removed in FWB by day 7 (e.g., clarithromycin,
558 codeine, flufenamic acid, irbesartan, ketoprofen). Besides this, other PP showed high
559 concentration reduction rates (e.g., 84% for eprosartan and 76% sulfamethoxazole).

560 From a qualitative point of view, we would like to remark that FWB reduced to zero
561 some PP that are relevant in terms of the environmental risk assessment. Some of them
562 due to the great demand and use, such as codeine (analgesic), flufenamic acid (analgesic),
563 sotolol, and timolol (cardiac condition and hypertension), and others, such as
564 clarithromycin, due to its potential role in worsening the current antimicrobial resistance
565 crisis [55]. Similarly, the FWBB treatment showed great effectivity in the long term by
566 removing acridine in 21 days.

567 It is important to highlight that although there were no differences in the total PP
568 removal rate between FWB and FWBB, it is necessary to consider the extra inputs needed
569 to create the biofilm (we need to consider the specialized staff's working hours, the extra
570 facilities such as temperature-controlled chamber and the energy in terms of electricity
571 for create and maintain the biofilm growth conditions). These disadvantages allow us to
572 discriminate in favour of the use of the NBS based in the floating wetlands enhanced with
573 biochar without biofilm, at least under the conditions used in this study. In addition,

574 although out of this study's aim, a long-term treatment performance needs to be
575 considered in future research lines to provide an integrated cost-benefit NBS assessment.

576 Regarding NBS and pharmaceutical pollution removal, several research gaps to be
577 addressed have been claimed, including the ecotoxicity evaluation of NBSs' effluents
578 [56]. The ecotoxicological approach considered in this study has several advantages
579 confronting the chemical assessment. First of all, we have confirmed the lethal effect of
580 the WWTP effluent as a cocktail of contaminants. We cannot give any responsibility to a
581 specific PP but to the toxic mixture. If the WWTP effluent can affect zooplankton
582 organisms to the extent of 20% of the population, that means great environmental impact
583 at that specific point. Although the natural dilution process should always be present, in
584 areas where the streams and rivers' flow decrease largely in summer (seasonally), as in
585 the Mediterranean region [45,57,58], special actions should be taken to reduce PP
586 concentrations in WWTP effluents as a point-source of pollution. The NBS, as the ones
587 we proposed, would be an option to reduce the environmental risk of WWTP effluent due
588 to PP. The changes and variability in rainfall predicted by the Climate Change projections
589 will affect surface water flows and will increase pollutant concentrations, reducing water
590 quality [59].

591 In addition, the toxicological assessment using a behavioural biomarker, such as
592 avoidance behaviour, informs about the organisms' reaction to the toxic cocktail, and,
593 therefore, gives additional and ecologically relevant information. Chemical cues are used
594 by aquatic organisms in several ways, such as to search for food or avoid predators, but
595 most of them to select optimal habitats [60]. WWTP effluents will create areas that the
596 organism will try to avoid (depending on the organism's capacity to move or to escape),
597 which can lead to specific habitat selection and, therefore, uneven organisms' spatial
598 distribution [61,62]. Besides, these direct effects of pharmaceuticals on the traits and
599 abundance of one species can cascade through a community, indirectly affecting other
600 species [6]. In our case, we have confirmed that zooplankton organisms are avoiding those
601 compartments with wastewater, while if the wastewater passes through the NBS (in our
602 case, FWB), the mentioned behaviour does not occur. That means that the NBS reduces
603 the negative effect of wastewater, likely PP polluted, on aquatic ecosystems. This kind of
604 bioassays are even more relevant considering that many transformation products are not
605 included in standard chemical analyses and, sometimes, they are more toxic than the
606 parent product [56]. The ecotoxicological assessment shows the environmental risk
607 reduction when NBSs are implemented and informs about their efficiency. Moreover,

608 behaviour is considered a non-destructive biomarker that can be used as an early warning
609 signal before major environmental impacts occur [63].

610 Although the present study has some limitations (such as the use of static systems
611 microcosms and testing the effects just on one type of zooplankton organism) we provided
612 scientific evidence on the NBS efficiency in PP pollution removal. Furthermore, the
613 efficiency has been confirmed not only with the chemical approach but also with the
614 toxicological approach, presenting the biological repercussions beyond the concentration
615 data. With this ecotoxicological approach, we also highlight the relevance of considering
616 the toxic cocktail, as a whole, in risk assessment. As cost-effective systems, they are also
617 feasible solutions for regions with limited financial resources [64]. For more severe cases,
618 with highly toxic pollutants, NBS can help through the implementation of hybrid systems,
619 e.g. floating wetlands working in conjunction with subsurface systems and sand filtration
620 systems, which will improve the final quality of the treated water [65].

621

622 **5. Conclusion**

623 The proposed nature-based solutions were efficient in reducing PP concentration from
624 wastewater (over 40% removal rate) and reducing its negative effects, as a toxic
625 “cocktail” on aquatic organisms. The results presented in this study give scientific
626 evidence on the usefulness of the proposed NBSs as quaternary treatments and their likely
627 role in solving global water-related environmental problems concerning micropollutants.
628 The best performance was obtained with the floating wetlands enhanced with biochar
629 within a lapse consistent with standard hydraulic retention times (Fig. 3).
630 Bioaugmentation with the microorganisms used in this study did not improve the global
631 efficiency in reducing pharmaceuticals pollution, at least under our conditions. It is
632 crucial to consider the improvement of the wastewater treatment plants’ sustainability
633 with quaternary treatments funded by NBS. Further research must be undertaken to
634 increase NBSs’ efficiency, reduce costs, and break down technical and political barriers
635 to improve their implementation.

636

637

638 **Data availability**

639 Data will be made available on request and, partially at the institutional repository of
640 scientific production of the University of Jaén (RUJA).

641

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652

653 **CRedit authorship contribution statement**

654 **María Rodríguez-Santamarina** Investigation, Data curation, Writing original draft;
655 **Bienvenida Gilbert López;** Data curation, Writing – review & editing. **Ana Belén**
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658 **Eugenia López Valcárcel:** Investigation, Data curation, Formal analysis, Writing –
659 review & editing. **Raquel Jimenez-Melero:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Writing –
660 review & editing. **Gema Parra:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Project
661 administration, Resources, Supervision, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing –
662 review & editing.

663

664 **Declaration of competing interest**

665 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
666 relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

667

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671 **References.**

672

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- 918 Highlights:
- 919
- 920 - Floating wetlands enhanced with biochar were proposed as Nature Based
- 921 Solutions (NBSs)
- 922 - Proposed NBSs were efficient in removing pharmaceuticals at the microcosm scale
- 923 - NBS efficiency was assessed under chemical and ecotoxicological approaches.
- 924 - Selected NBS reduces wastewater toxic effects under standard hydraulic retention times

1 **A combined chemical and ecotoxicological approach to asses Nature-based**
2 **Solutions efficiency in removing pharmaceuticals using microcosms.**

3
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23 **Keywords:** Contaminants of emerging concern, floating wetlands, biochar, chemical,
24 and toxicological assessment.

25
26 **ABSTRACT**

27 Pharmaceutical products (PP) are considered contaminants of emerging concern, and
28 their discharge into the environment has increased due to both, human and veterinary use.
29 These drugs entered freshwater ecosystems and remain physiologically active, posing
30 potential negative effects on aquatic ecosystems. As conventional plants for wastewater
31 treatment are not designed to remove most of these micropollutants, the development of
32 strategies for sustainable management is essential and nature-based solutions (NBS) will
33 be useful in removing pollution, simultaneously benefiting people and nature. This study
34 aims to assess the effectiveness of PP removal of different NBSs implemented at a

35 microcosm scale from chemical and ecotoxicological points of view. Proposed NBSs
36 were based on floating wetlands with improvements based on the use of biochar and
37 bioaugmentation (biofilm coating). The proposed NBSs were able to reduce up to 90%
38 of the total PP concentration after the whole experimental period (42 days). However,
39 considering a regular hydraulic retention time (7 days), the higher PP removal rate (55%),
40 took place in the microcosms with floating wetlands enhanced with biochar (FWB),
41 followed by the floating wetlands enhanced with biofilm-coated biochar (FWBB) (51%)
42 and the floating wetland (FW) (42%). The selected NBS (FWB) has also been assessed
43 through the toxicological approach, and the acute and behavioural effects of the
44 wastewater were also reduced after 7 days. The proposed solution will benefit both nature
45 and society, reducing PP pollution and enhancing water resource quality. The results
46 obtained with the ecotoxicological approach highlight the relevance of considering the
47 toxic cocktail, as a whole, in environmental risk assessment and the use of behavioural
48 biomarkers for spotlighting its ecological consequences.

49

50 **1. Introduction**

51

52 In 2009, Rockström et al. presented the conceptual framework of planetary boundaries
53 that defines a series of thresholds to achieve the stability of the Earth [1]. One of these
54 boundaries is the contamination by novel entities or contaminants of emerging concern
55 (CECs). The term was defined by [2], which encompasses chemicals, such as drugs, and
56 other new types of engineered materials or organisms not previously known to the Earth
57 system, as well as natural elements, for example, heavy metals, mobilized by
58 anthropogenic activities and accumulated at high concentrations. These toxic substances
59 reach freshwater and marine ecosystems, likely affecting aquatic organisms, potentially
60 causing alterations in trophic webs, and affecting ecosystems functioning and stability
61 [3]. In addition, likely this pollution will intensify in the future, due to the increase in the
62 activity of the chemical industry over time [4].

63 PP are considered CECs and their discharge into the environment has increased due to
64 the human population increase and aging and their veterinary use [5]. These drugs that
65 have entered freshwater ecosystems remain physiologically active, disturbing the
66 ecosystems [6]. The number of studies on the toxic effects of PP that reach aquatic
67 environments has increased recently [7–9] highlighting the significant ecological and
68 health risks and the necessary research on effective mitigation strategies [10]. Therefore,

69 PPs have contributed significantly to aquatic pollution, with urban wastewater being one
70 of the largest pollution sources [11].

71 Conventional plants for wastewater treatment were not designed to remove most of
72 the CECs [11]. Additionally, until now, they have not been subjected to specific
73 regulations regarding their limit of presence in water, so there is no monitoring of these
74 compounds in the different environmental compartments (water, sediments, biota) [12].
75 However, the European Council recently adopts new rules for more efficient treatments,
76 and by 2045 member states will have to apply additional treatments to
77 remove micropollutants (such as pharmaceuticals and cosmetics), known as quaternary
78 treatment [13]. In this concern, developing strategies for sustainable water resources
79 management is essential. Given this, some studies have called for further monitoring
80 studies to better understand the impact on environmental contamination by
81 pharmaceuticals and to evaluate the necessity for quaternary treatments, such as the NBS
82 [14]. NBS are actions to protect, sustainably manage, and restore natural and modified
83 ecosystems that address societal challenges effectively and adaptively, simultaneously
84 benefiting people and nature [15]. Two of the key aspects in NBS are the integrity of the
85 ecosystem-society binomial, as well as the evident link with the Sustainable Development
86 Goals (SDGs), since it is not possible to understand the progress of society without
87 considering the preservation of the environment and the sustainability of natural resources
88 [16].

89 The aquatic plant community can purify water naturally, improving its quality. They
90 are based on the natural processes of biological filtering of water as it passes through
91 shallow areas and permeable soils. Emerging plants like cattails (*Thypha* sp.) absorb and
92 eliminate nutrients such as N and P. They can also decompose contaminants and toxins
93 from sediment and water by incorporating them into their biomass. But they also provide
94 shelter and surface to other organisms, such as microorganisms, plankton, and fish that
95 can help with the absorption of nutrients and the decomposition of pollutants that reach
96 the aquatic systems [17]. So, they can be considered NBS when used to remove pollution
97 from wastewater [18,19]. NBS designed to improve water quality, such as the artificial or
98 constructed wetlands, are tools that allow the sustainable use of water resources and the
99 protection of aquatic systems threatened by pollutants and whose effectiveness has been
100 verified in a wide variety of experiences and situations [20]. The use of the plants and
101 microorganisms' natural capacity to decompose pollutants through biological processes
102 is known as bioremediation and is part of the processes that classify NBS as amelioration

103 solutions (amelioration-NBS type, following [21]) and are considered a low-cost and
104 environmentally friendly option [22]. The use of artificial or constructed wetlands as
105 NBS, specifically floating wetlands, has been previously reported as an efficient strategy
106 to eliminate pollutants [23]. For example, a floating treatment wetland (FTW) was used
107 as a strategy for attenuating the pollutant concentration in a crude oil wastewater pit,
108 being successful in removing organics, hydrocarbons, total dissolved solids, and heavy
109 metals [24].

110 To improve the PP removal capacity of artificial wetlands, we can incorporate
111 adsorbent elements, such as biochar, a carbon-rich material that can be prepared from
112 various organic waste feedstocks, such as agricultural plant residues and sewage sludge
113 [25]. It has been demonstrated that biochar prepared from olive oil wastes eliminated
114 emerging contaminants from water at laboratory scale [26]. The PP elimination yields
115 vary according to the PP typology between 40-96%. The properties of these materials
116 (physical, chemical, and biological) make them optimal for wastewater decontamination
117 treatments [27] [28][29–31]. El Barkaoui and collaborators reviewed the use of Biochar
118 in constructed wetlands in the literature and stated that the removal efficiency of
119 pollutants in constructed wetlands is affected by several factors, such as substrate
120 chemical and physical properties, oxygenation, and hydraulic retention time, among
121 others [31]. The use of biochar as an innovative amendment can enhance the removal
122 efficiencies of nitrogen, emerging organic contaminants, and metals in constructed
123 wetlands treatment systems, simultaneously mitigating the greenhouse effect and
124 reducing the land requirement of these nature-based solutions [28].

125 Another removal enhancement strategy is based on using specific microorganisms
126 capable of reducing PP. These organisms can be found in ecosystems with a history of
127 pollution by PP [32] and they have been used in bioaugmentation lab experiments [33].
128 Although it is a little-studied field, some authors have studied the interactions between
129 biochars and microbial biofilms, analysing the potential advantages and disadvantages of
130 this association in the elimination of some types of contaminants [34,35]. For example, a
131 study also confirmed that FTWs inoculated with bacteria possessed hydrocarbon
132 degradation capability [36]. The role of the presence of strong increases in polar
133 functional groups associated with stable biofilms in pharmaceutical contaminant
134 purification systems still presents important unknowns that are partly intended to be
135 analysed in this work. These functional groups are also present in microbial biomass and
136 other authors have that these chemical groups are involved in the adsorption of

137 pharmaceutical and personal care products [37]. On the other hand, conventional biochar
138 obtained by simple carbonization usually has low porosity, which limits its adsorption
139 capacity, while their chemical activation is expensive [38]. For this reason, we aimed to
140 assess if biochar enhanced with microbial biofilm could improve its adsorption capacity
141 against pharmaceuticals.

142 We hypothesised that both strategies, the use of biochar and the use of biofilm-coated
143 biochar, enhance the floating wetland capacity of removing PP, and reduce the toxic effect
144 from wastewater, functioning as innovative NBSs.

145 This study aims to assess the effectiveness of PP removal of the different NBSs
146 implemented at microcosms scale, firstly from a chemical point of view analysing the
147 rate of PP removal; and secondly, from an ecotoxicological point of view, analysing the
148 toxicity of the wastewater, before and after the NBS, using standard and innovative
149 toxicological protocols. The combination of both assessments is key to informing
150 quantitatively and qualitatively on the NBSs' efficiency.

151

152

153 **2. Material and methods**

154

155 *2.1. Chemicals and reagents*

156

157 A total of 107 pharmaceuticals and some of their relevant transformation products
158 were included in the monitoring (Table S1). The selection of the analytes was based on
159 those commonly found in wastewater effluents from the area [39] as well as some
160 compounds included in the European Watch List published by the European Parliament
161 in 2022. Analytical standards (purity \geq 98%) were purchased from Dr. Ehrenstorfer
162 (Augsburg, Germany) and Merck Group (Darmstadt, Germany). A surrogate standard
163 solution of difenoxuron in methanol (MeOH) was used as an internal standard (IS) for
164 extraction quality control check. Acetonitrile (ACN), MeOH, and water (LC-MS grade)
165 were acquired from Merck Group (Darmstadt, Germany). Formic acid (FA) was supplied
166 by Honeywell Fluka (Buchs, Switzerland). Oasis HLB SPE cartridges (200 mg, 6 mL)
167 were acquired from Waters (Milford, MA, USA).

168

169 *2.2. Biochar characterization*

170

171 The ground biochar used in the study is generated from pruning biomass using the
172 hydrothermal carbonization process and it was provided by INGELIA S.L. The company
173 provides also the general characterization of moisture (7%), ash content (5-10% dry
174 weight), total carbon (55-60 % ash-free dry weight-AFDW), total nitrogen (1-1.5%
175 AFDW), volatiles (45-55 % on carbon) and lower heating value (LHV 22-23 MJ/kg). The
176 biochar bulk or apparent density is 750 kg m⁻³.

177

178 2.3 Biofilm-coated biochar process

179

180 A ubiquitous strain isolated from wastewater from the province of Jaén [40] and
181 registered in the Spanish collection of type cultures (CECT) was selected to evaluate its
182 ability to form biofilms that improve the adsorption capacity of PP by the pruning biochar
183 pellets chosen for this work. *Rhodotorula mucilaginosa* 1S1 CECT 13212 had already
184 shown a good biosorption capacity for Ag(I) [41] based on a strong presence of hydroxyl,
185 carbonyl, amino, methyl, and methylene functional groups, which suggested that it could
186 provide an improvement in the adsorption of the organic molecules evaluated in this
187 research. Using Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FT-IR) we analysed whether
188 biochar enhanced with microbial biofilm could improve its adsorption capacity against
189 PP. Before starting the tests, the pellets were subjected to light sterilization at 85 °C for
190 48 h. Starting with a 24-h pre-inoculum on YPG medium (yeast, 10 g L⁻¹; peptone, 10 g
191 L⁻¹; glucose, 20 g L⁻¹), batch tests were started at 27 °C and 150 rpm. The biochar was
192 placed in a sterile mesh to prevent damage from the agitation conditions. After 10 days
193 of growth, the pellets were washed repeatedly with 0.1 M NaCl and under shaking
194 conditions to remove any remains of the nutrient medium. Finally, samples were taken
195 and fixed with 2.5% glutaraldehyde, they were dehydrated with increasing concentrations
196 of acetone and after drying at 35 °C, they were metalized with carbon for analysis by
197 scanning electron microscopy (SEM) with the idea of confirming the colonization of the
198 microorganism on the surface of the biochar. In parallel, an analysis of FT-IR by
199 attenuated total refraction (ATR) was carried out on the biochar pellets previously ground
200 in porcelain mortar (before and after growing biofilm), to check the presence of functional
201 groups. Both, biochar and biofilm-coated biochar, were used in batch tests to determine
202 the adsorption of carbamazepine, diclofenac, and sulfamethoxazole under laboratory
203 conditions (Table S2) and analysed by FT-IR. Both materials were later used in the
204 microcosm-scale experiment framed in the NBS proposed in this work.

205

206 *2.4 Microcosms setup and stabilization phase*

207

208 Twenty polypropylene containers (556 x 356 x 304 mm) were used as microcosms.
209 They were placed in the experimental wetland, an area at the University of Jaén (Spain)
210 devoted to research under outdoor conditions. They were filled with previously
211 dechlorinated tap water, reaching a final volume of 30 L. Floating wetlands were
212 assembled following the supplier instructions with 6 plants of *Thypha* sp. species inserted
213 in the plastic tile in each microcosm (QUARQ ENTERPRISE S.A.) (Microcosms'
214 pictures in Supplementary material **Fig. S1**). The microcosms were stabilized for 5 weeks,
215 allowing the plants to develop before wastewater exposure. Microcosms were monitored
216 weekly, using the YSI-556MPS multiparametric probe to measure: temperature (°C), pH,
217 conductivity (mS/cm), and dissolved oxygen (%). Aquaflor fluorometer (Turner Designs)
218 was used to measure chlorophyll-*a* content (Chl-*a*).

219

220 *2.5. Microcosms wastewater exposure phase*

221

222 After 5 weeks of stabilization, the microcosms were exposed to wastewater (WW)
223 from the Santa Catalina Wastewater Treatment Plant (secondary treatment, Jaén, Spain).
224 Static systems were used in this study. The treatments studied were as follows. **Null**
225 **treatment**: microcosms without floating wetland, with WW; **Control FW**: microcosms
226 with floating wetland with stabilization phase water; **FW**: microcosms with floating
227 wetland with WW; **FWB**: microcosms with floating wetland with WW, improved with
228 biochar; **FWBB**: microcosms with floating wetland with WW, improved with biofilm
229 coated biochar. Four replicates for each treatment were established.

230

231 In those treatments with biochar, the microcosms received 60 g of biochar distributed
232 in 6 permeable bags located close to the *Thypha* sp. radicular section (**Fig. S1**). The
233 exposure phase lasted 7 weeks, and samples were taken every 3 days during the first
234 week, and then once per week until the end of the study: days 0, 3, 7, 14, 21, 28, 35, and
235 42. The chemical, physical, and biological parameters mentioned in the stabilization
236 phase were also measured on each sampling day during the exposure phase. Further, water
237 samples were taken from each microcosm for subsequent semiquantitative nutrient
238 analysis (nitrate, using the VISOCOLOR™ ECO Rapid Kits; Phosphate content using
QUANTOFIX™ Quick Strips. Additionally, samples were taken in 1 L amber glass

239 bottles from each microcosm to carry out the analysis of pharmaceuticals by liquid
240 chromatography/mass spectrometry (LC-MS). The bottles were filled with a syringe to a
241 volume of 750 mL and closed with Teflon caps. After that, the bottles were superficially
242 disinfected with ethanol, labelled, and finally frozen at -20 °C until analysed.

243

244 *2.6 Monitoring of pharmaceuticals*

245 *2.6.1 Sample preparation*

246 Samples were defrosted and filtered (cellulose, 0.45 µm pore size). A solid-phase
247 extraction (SPE) procedure, based on our previous studies [39] [42] was applied. Briefly,
248 200 mL of treated water were spiked with an IS solution and extracted using an Oasis
249 HLB cartridge. The SPE cartridge was preconditioned with 4 mL of MeOH and 8 mL of
250 H₂O (LC-MS grade). After sample loading, the cartridge was dried under vacuum for
251 30 min. The elution of the analytes was performed with two aliquots of 4 mL of MeOH.
252 The extract was then evaporated in a water bath (37 °C) under a gentle nitrogen stream
253 (15 psi) until dryness (30 min approx.), and reconstituted with 2 mL of MeOH. Before
254 injection in the LC-MS, a 1:50 dilution of the extract using Milli-Q water was carried out.
255 Therefore, the complete procedure involves a global 2:1 preconcentration of the WW
256 sample [42].

257

258 *2.6.2 Sample analysis by LC-MS and Quantification*

259

260 Instrumental analysis was carried out using the same conditions as previously reported
261 [42]. A Thermo Vanquish Flex LC system (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA,
262 USA) coupled with a Q-Exactive Orbitrap (Thermo Fisher Scientific) mass spectrometer
263 was employed for sample analysis. A Zorbax Rapid Resolution High Definition (RRHD)
264 Eclipse Plus C18 (2.1 mm × 50 mm, 1.8 µm, Agilent Technologies, Wilmington, DE,
265 USA) analytical column was used for chromatographic separation. A mixture of ultrapure
266 water (0.1% FA, eluent A) and MeOH (0.1% FA, eluent B) was used as the mobile phase.
267 The gradient employed was as follows: initial conditions, 10% B for 0.7 min; within 4.0
268 min, linear increase from 10% to 50%; within 17 min, linear increase to 95% B; kept
269 constant at 95% B for 8 min; within 0.1 min decreased to 10% B; and kept constant for
270 column equilibration during 5 min. The total analysis run time was 30 min.

271 The mass spectrometer was equipped with a heated electrospray ionization source
272 (HESI) operating in both positive and negative modes (individual analysis). The HESI

273 parameters were as follows: sheath gas flow rate 55 units; aux gas flow rate 15 units;
274 spray voltage 3.5 kV (2.5 kV, negative ionization); capillary temperature 300 °C; S-lens
275 RF level 60; and aux gas heater temperature 350 °C. The detection of the compounds was
276 performed using a combination of full-scan (FS) and data-dependent acquisition (DDA)
277 for MS/MS spectra. For FS analysis, data were acquired at a resolving power of 70,000
278 FWHM; the automatic gain control (AGC) target was set at 3×10^6 with a maximum
279 injection time (IT) of 100 ms, and a scan range from m/z 65 to 950. For DDA, resolution
280 was 17,500 FWHM; AGC target 2×10^5 ; Maximum IT 100 ms; loop count 5; maximum
281 number of ions to trigger after FS based on ion abundance (TopN) 5; isolation window 1
282 Da; and normalized collision energy (NCE) set at 35. Xcalibur 3.0 and Trace Finder 3.3
283 (Thermo Fisher Scientific) software were used for qualitative and quantitative data
284 analysis.

285 The methodology was validated by assessing linearity, method quantification limits
286 (MQLs), matrix effects, trueness (expressed as recoveries), and precision (expressed as
287 relative standard deviations, RSDs). Detailed validation results for the 107 compounds
288 studied can be found elsewhere [42]. For quantification purposes, the concentration of
289 the PP was calculated by interpolating the obtained peak area in matrix-matched
290 calibration curves (range 0.005 – 5 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$).

291

292

293 2.7. Toxicological assessment

294

295 Two toxicological tests were carried out using *Daphnia magna* as the test organism to
296 evaluate the environmental risk that wastewater PP cocktails may pose to aquatic biota.

297 Firstly, an acute toxicity test based on the OECD protocol [43] was carried out to find
298 the wastewater LD50 (lethal dilution) for the *D. magna* population cultured at the
299 University of Jaén. *D. magna* was reared in mineral water in the laboratory for many
300 years using the microalga *Scenedesmus obliquus* (Turpin) Kützing 1833 as food
301 (Chemical Engineering Laboratory, University of Jaén). These algae were routinely
302 maintained in 3 N-BBM*V culture media at pH 8.3–8.5 (modified from CCAP, Scotland).
303 Both, *D. magna* and *S. obliquus* were cultured in a temperature-controlled chamber
304 (ARALAB-600PHL-LED) and under the same conditions (20 °C and a 12:12 h light:dark
305 cycle). Enriched mineral water (EMW) with thiamine (0.075 g L⁻¹), vitamin B12 (0.010
306 g L⁻¹), biotin (0.0075 g L⁻¹), and sodium selenite (0.010 g L⁻¹) was used following Díaz-

307 Báez et al (2008) culture protocol. WW from the Santa Catalina wastewater treatment
308 plant effluent (WWTP) was used to prepare the treatments for the acute toxicity test:
309 Control treatment (100% EMW used for daphnids culture, also used to make the
310 dilutions); 25% WW treatment (25% WW + 75% EMW); 50% WW treatment (50% WW
311 + 50% EMW); 75% WW treatment (75% WW + 25% EMW), and 100% WW treatment
312 (100% WW). Ten daphnids (<24 h) were added to each replicate (3 replicates in each
313 treatment). Therefore, 150 individuals were used and maintained under the same culture
314 conditions of light and temperature (ARALAB-600PHL-LED chamber) but without food.
315 Survival was checked after 24 hours and 48 hours.

316 Secondly, two avoidance behaviour tests were conducted to assess the effects on *D.*
317 *magna* behaviour. In the first one, we use the WW, and in the second one, we use the
318 water from FWB microcosms taken by the end of the exposure period (day 42). We
319 decided to use the FWB treatment as representative of the innovative NBSs proposed,
320 and due to the limitation of only being able to perform an HeMHAS experiment. We have
321 followed the methodology used by Moreira & collaborators [44] and the HeMHAS
322 system (Heterogeneous Multi-Habitat Assay System). This system allows a non-forced
323 exposure to toxicants and the analysis of the avoidance or escape behaviour, when the
324 individuals select the most convenient/safe compartment. In the first test, the dilutions set
325 was: i) 100% *D. magna* culture water (EMW), ii) 50% wastewater from the treatment
326 plant (WW) + 50% EMW, and iii) 100% WW (Fig. 1a). In the second test, carried out to
327 confirm the effect of the water from the FWB, the dilutions set was: i) 100% EMW, ii)
328 50% water from microcosms FWB + 50% EMW and iii) 100% water from microcosms
329 FWB (Fig. 1b). Ten adult daphnids were placed in each compartment, with the gates open
330 allowing the movement of individuals along the dilution gradient. Individuals in each
331 compartment were counted every half hour until reaching 4 hours. The last check was
332 carried out after 24 hours. HeMHAS system allows to perform 3 replicates per trial, using
333 150 individuals on the whole.

334

335 2.8 Statistical analysis

336

337 The microcosm stabilization period results were analyzed with a Generalized linear
338 model (GLM) and Tukey post hoc to test differences among microcosm concerning the
339 measured variables (physicochemical and biological variables). RStudio software was
340 used.

341 A shade chart was plotted to visualize the concentration patterns of PP on the different
342 treatments over time. A non-metric multidimensional scaling (nMDS) ordination plot,
343 based on the Bray-Curtis similarities among treatments, was carried out; the closer points
344 are to each other the more similar the PP composition of the different NBSs [45]. Success
345 of the ordination was measured by a stress coefficient [46].

346 To detect differences in PP composition between treatments over time, a multivariate
347 analysis of the PP data was performed using a Permutational Analysis of Variance
348 (PERMANOVA). A two-way design was implemented, that is, the factor NBSs with 4
349 levels (Null; FW; FWB; FWBB), the factor time with 3 levels (0, 3 and 7 days) and the
350 interaction between them. This analysis was undertaken with 9999 permutations on Bray-
351 Curtis similarity matrices.

352 In addition, a Similarity Percentage Analyses (SIMPER) was performed to identify the
353 discriminant PPs between treatments (i.e., which PP contributes to the differences
354 between PP assemblages) [45]. PRIMER v7 software was used to perform all these
355 analyses. Data were previously fourth root transformed in order to reduce the influence
356 of more abundant PP and increase the influence of rarer PP in the analysis [46].

357 Several two-way Generalized Linear Model (GLM), with Poisson distribution and log-
358 link function, were performed [47] to detect the potential effects of NBSs and time and
359 their interaction on the abundances of PP.

360 Acute toxicity test results were analysed using the non-parametric test Kruskal-Wallis
361 test to evaluate differences among treatments (non-normal distributed data). To perform
362 multiple comparisons between groups, the Dunn test with Holm adjustment was applied.

363 Avoidance behaviour test results were analysed using analysis of variance (ANOVA)
364 to assess differences in means among treatments (normal distributed data). To further
365 investigate which specific groups were different, a Tukey Honest Significant Difference
366 (HSD) test was conducted

367

368 **3. Results**

369

370 *3.1. Biofilm-coated biochar process*

371

372 The preliminary results obtained in the biological activation tests of the biochar
373 demonstrated that the yeast *R. mucilaginosa* 1S1 CECT 13212 had a good capacity to

374 promote biofilm formation on the mentioned organic support (**Fig. S2**), showing a strong
375 release of exopolysaccharides (EPS) by the yeast and a uniform distribution.

376 On the other hand, the FT-IR spectra obtained before and after the formation of
377 microbial biofilm showed a slight increase in the intensity of the functional groups
378 concerning the original biochar with a predominance of hydroxyl groups associated with
379 two regions with intervals located at 3000-3300 cm^{-1} and at 900-1200 cm^{-1} ; methyl (CH_3)
380 and methylene (CH_2) groups derived from C-H bonds in the regions between 3000-2800
381 cm^{-1} and 1300-1500 cm^{-1} ; carbonyl ($\text{C}=\text{O}$) and amino (NH) groups associated with
382 amides I and II in the region between 1500 and 1800 cm^{-1} ; and phosphate groups (P-O)
383 represented in the bands in the region located between 900 and 1300 cm^{-1} .

384 Table S2 shows the results obtained in the batch adsorption tests and it was observed
385 that the biochar associated with microbial biofilm had improved the adsorption in the case
386 of diclofenac while the other two compounds have been absorbed slightly worse. In
387 general, the batch adsorption stage caused significant changes in the FTIR spectra (**Fig.**
388 **S3**), including changes in intensity and shifts in the bands. The bands located between
389 1300 and 600 cm^{-1} underwent significant changes, and this shows that the groups
390 associated with this region were involved in the adsorption of the pharmaceutical
391 compounds studied.

392 These results allow us to confirm that the biochar alone presented a wide range of
393 functional groups that can interact with the PP. Likewise, *R. mucilaginosa* 1S1 CECT
394 13212 and the microbial biofilm created have also been shown to increase the number of
395 functional groups, leading to a potential increase in PP biosorption capacity by the
396 biochar.

397

398 *3.2. Microcosms stabilization phase and wastewater exposure phase*

399

400 During the stabilization phase, the microcosm showed similar values in the physic-
401 chemical and biological variables, allowing the macrophyte stabilization and growth
402 (mean \pm SD, Temperature: 23.98 ± 0.85 °C; D.O.: 69.39 ± 2.55 %; pH: 5.83 ± 0.25 ;
403 Conductivity: 0.92 ± 0.07 mS/cm; and Chlorophyll *a*: 48.56 ± 33.58 mg L^{-1}). Concerning
404 the exposure phase, at the end of this period (day 42), there were differences between the
405 Null treatment and the rest of the treatments just in pH (**Table S3**).

406

407 *3.3. Chemical assessment*

408

409 The wastewater (WW) samples were from the Jaén treatment plant (115,000
410 inhabitants). Nine compounds showed saturated signals in the LC-MS analysis (caffeine,
411 antipyrine, paracetamol, theobromine, theophylline, naproxen, valsartan, nicotine, and
412 cotinine). Therefore, they were discarded from the study due to the impossibility of
413 reinjecting diluted sample extracts for their proper quantification. Overall, a total of 39
414 active substances were quantified in WW samples: (2-ethylidene-1-5-dimethyl-3-3-
415 diphenyl-pyrrolidine perchlorate, 9(10h)-acridone, acridine, atenolol, bupropion,
416 carbamazepine, carbamazepine 10-11-epoxide, citalopram, clarithromycin, cocaine,
417 codeine, diclofenac, diphenhydramine, eprosartan, flecainide, fluconazole, flufenamic
418 acid, gabapentin, gemfibrozil, irbesartan, ketamine, ketoprofen, lamotrigine, lidocaine,
419 mepivacaine, metformin, methadone, morphine, N-methylephedrine, O-
420 desmethylvenlafaxine, sotalol, sulfamethoxazole, sulfapyridine, sulpiride, telmisartan,
421 timolol, tramadol, trimethoprim, and venlafaxine). Ten of these positive findings
422 corresponded to substances included in the Watch List for surface water monitoring [48]:
423 clarithromycin, diclofenac, clotrimazole, fluconazole, O-desmethylvenlafaxine,
424 venlafaxine, metformin, ciprofloxacin, sulfamethoxazole, and trimethoprim.

425 After the exposure period in those microcosms without any NBS (treatment Null), 4
426 pharmaceutical products were not detected after 3 days (2-ethylidene-1-5-dimethyl-3-3-
427 diphenyl-pyrrolidine, bupropion, citalopram and cocaine). These PP were not included in
428 the heat maps created for the whole experimental period (**Fig. 2**), where the colour
429 intensity was used to represent PP average concentration in each treatment. The data were
430 separated into two different concentration ranges, creating two heat maps for a better
431 visualization of the PP removal process (below and over 100 ng L⁻¹, **Fig. 2a and Fig. 2b**
432 **respectively**).

433 We decided to further analyse the changes in PP composition in the first 7 days of the
434 experiment as, under WWTP regular conditions, water flows in through the artificial
435 wetland with an average hydraulic retention time of around this lapse of time. Considering
436 the global PP concentration, the removal rate by day 7 indicates that those NBSs with
437 biochar showed higher efficiency. The higher PP removal rate took place in the
438 microcosms with FWB, followed by the FWBB, and significantly different from the FW
439 and Null treatment removal rates ($F_{(3,7)}=72.632; p < 0.001$; **Fig. 3**). The non-metric multi-
440 dimensional scaling (nMDS) ordination plot based on the Bray-Curtis similarities (Figure
441 4) shown a gradient in PP structure from day 0 to day 7 (along MDS axis 1) and related

442 to NBSs (along MDS axis 2). The 2-d stress level was low, 0.06, so this nMDS provides
443 an excellent representation in reduced dimensions. The PP composition of the FWB on
444 day 7 was different from the rest of the treatments on the same day and very different
445 from the PP composition at the beginning of the experiment. On day 3, the composition
446 of PP in FWB and FWBB were more similar to each other than to the rest of the
447 treatments.

448 Indeed, these results agreed with a two-way PERMANOVA which detected significant
449 differences in the PP composition between NBSs (Pseudo-F_(3,17) = 25,88; $p = 0.001$) and
450 a significant effect of the exposure time (Pseudo-F_(2,17) = 153.06; $p = 0.001$). The
451 interaction was also significant (Pseudo-F_(6,17) = 6.784; $p = 0.001$); in fact, as nMDS
452 shown, in all NBSs, PP composition changed over time, but these differences were less
453 noticeable for FWBB and more remarkable for FWB (**Fig. 4**).

454 Considering the individualized PP GLM results, the PP's concentrations were
455 significantly reduced by the treatments ($p < 0.05$), just Ketamine and Sulfapyridine
456 concentrations were not different among treatments ($\chi^2_{(3, 20)} = 2.43$; $p = 0.4881$ and $\chi^2_{(3, 20)}$
457 = 4.6101; $p = 0.2027$, respectively).

458 In **Table 1** the dissimilarity percentages values were presented, confirming that the
459 higher PP removal took place in the FWB microcosms, followed by the FWBB. To
460 elucidate which PPs contribute to the differentiation between treatments, a SIMPER was
461 performed. **Table 2** shows the discriminant PP among the wastewater treatment plant
462 (WWTP, day 0) and the treatments at day 7. To identify the PP that contributes the most
463 to the differentiation between groups, the focus should be on the Average Dissimilarity
464 column; they will also tend to be the PPs with the larger abundances. In addition, to detect
465 the best indicator of the differences between those groups, Diss/SD ratio should also be
466 considered, since it can sometimes indicate PP that are completely absent in one group
467 and with very consistent presence in the other, but with low abundance [45]. Checking
468 both indicators (i.e., Av. Diss. and Diss/SD), we observed that both treatments, FWB and
469 FWBB, were very effective in reducing or removing irbesartan, ketoprofen,
470 clarithromycin, diphenhydramine, and metformin, among others (**Table 2c-d**). However,
471 the SIMPER shows the discriminant PP among treatments in day 7 (**Table 3**), FWB
472 removed more efficiently codeine, flufenamic acid, sotalol, timolol and 9(10H)-acridone,
473 among others, than FWBB (**Table 3f**). All the NBS (FW, FWB, FWBB) were effective in
474 eliminating diphenhydramine and methadone in less than 3 days (**Fig. 2b**; **Table 3**), while
475 both PP were still in the Null microcosms by that time. Both FWB and FWBB were

476 effective in removing completely in less than 3 days ibersartan and N-methilephedirne.
477 FWBB was effective in removing completely in less than 3 days clarithromycin (Fig. 2a).

478

479 3.4. Toxicological assessment

480

481 3.4.1. Acute test

482

483 After 48 h *D. magna* exposed to wastewater showed lower survival than the control
484 (culture water). There was a 20% reduction in *D. magna* survival in those vessels with
485 100% WW (without dilution) compared to control vessels (culture water) (Fig. 5) ($\chi^2_{(4,15)} = 10.5; p = 0.0328$).

486

488 3.4.2. Avoidance behaviour tests

489

490 In the first avoidance behaviour test and after 24 hours of exposure, the number of
491 individuals in the compartments decreases as the dilution of WW decrease too, indicating
492 that individuals of *D. magna* are selecting compartments without WW, avoiding the
493 exposure to it (Fig. 6a; $F_{(4,10)} = 3.781; p = 0.0401$).

494 In the second avoidance behaviour test and after 24 hours of exposure, there were no
495 differences in the number of individuals among compartments, indicating that *D. magna*
496 individuals did not avoid the compartments with water from FWB microcosm, regardless
497 the dilution (Fig. 6b; $F_{(4,10)} = 2.009; p = 0.169$).

498

499 4. Discussion

500

501 Our results showed that the three proposed NBSs: FW, FWB and FWBB, enhanced
502 the PP removal from WW. However, the highest water quality improvement (higher PP
503 removal rate) was obtained with FWB treatment. This finding could be attributed to the
504 biochar adsorption capacity, which, as shown in Figure S2, has numerous active
505 functional groups.

506 The presence of the *R. mucilaginosa* 1S1 CECT 13212 in FWBB was also found to
507 have increased the PP removal but without differences compared to FWB. In general,
508 biological activation did not improve the adsorption capacity of the biochar, although, as

509 mentioned (section 3.3; caption Fig. S3), it seems to do so for some of the compounds,
510 such as tramadol, which usually involves the participation of O-H and C-O groups [49].

511 In general, the groups present in both the biochar and the biofilm involve the presence
512 of oxygen and nitrogen atoms. These atoms are also present in the molecules of the
513 compounds studied and this makes these molecules able to accept hydrogens while the
514 groups present in the adsorbent complex can donate hydrogens forming dipole-dipole
515 interactions known as hydrogen bonds [34]. Likewise, the fact proven in this work of the
516 presence of polar functional groups that have both positive and negative partial charges
517 indicates that the presence of electrostatic interactions may also be present in this case as
518 other authors have previously demonstrated [50][51]. The electrostatic interaction has a
519 strong dependence on the ionic strength of the medium but also on the pH, which in our
520 case remained slightly above neutrality and would therefore be facilitating this
521 mechanism by preventing the protonation of the functional groups allowing them to have
522 a negative charge [51]. Another mechanism that cannot be ruled out is the presence of
523 hydrophobic interactions, since non-polar groups tend to group, minimizing their contact
524 with water molecules. Finally, some authors have indicated that the pore filling of biochar
525 is also present among the bioremediation mechanisms of some pharmaceutical products
526 [34].

527 However, the lack of general improvement in the response of biofilm-coated biochar
528 might be explained by the heterogeneity of the plant matter used to manufacture the
529 biochars (state of vegetative maturity and nature of the plant residue) and also by the
530 heterogeneity of the resulting ground material [52]. The above could affect the particle
531 diameter or porosity, all of which could affect the final specific surface area and, therefore
532 the availability of the functional groups present in the biochar (biofilm-coated or not). At
533 the same time, this heterogeneity could affect biofilm formation by *R. mucilaginosa* 1S1,
534 so the coat may not have been uniform. Finally, all of this could mean that the
535 predominant factor in PP adsorption was the specific characteristics of the ground biochar
536 in each case, above the biological activation caused by the microbial biofilm. To what
537 extent it is interesting to biologically coat a biochar and quantify its final contribution to
538 PP adsorption should be studied more thoroughly in the future since the data suggest that
539 a longer activation over time can generate much more active and stable biofilms in real
540 conditions which can undoubtedly significantly increase the adsorption capacity of
541 organic molecules by biochar.

542 During the stabilization period (no exposure) all microcosms showed similar
543 environmental and biological variable values, which allows us to defend the experimental
544 design and initial conditions for the later exposure period. While, at the end of the
545 exposure to wastewater, the microcosms showed statistical differences just in pH, being
546 NULL microcosms which showed higher pH values. The other treatments with NBS
547 showed similar data. So, biochar and biofilm-coated biochar addition to floating wetlands
548 did not generate differences between NBS treatments, at least for the measured
549 environmental variables.

550 Several PP were removed in the microcosms with no NBS (Null treatment). This is
551 consistent with previous studies describing that some organic contaminants suffer
552 photodegradation through abiotic reactions under outdoor conditions [53,54].

553 Diverse PP removal efficiency was observed among treatments. Although PP
554 concentration decreased at all NBS microcosms, the FWB treatment was the most
555 effective. The chemical assessment allows us to select the most efficient treatment from
556 those proposed. The use of floating wetlands enhanced with biochar at a microcosms scale
557 and the confirmation of its PP removal capacity allows us to defend it to be used at a
558 larger scale. Several PP were completely removed in FWB by day 7 (e.g., clarithromycin,
559 codeine, flufenamic acid, irbesartan, ketoprofen). Besides this, other PP showed high
560 concentration reduction rates (e.g., 84% for eprosartan and 76% sulfamethoxazole).

561 From a qualitative point of view, we would like to remark that FWB reduced to zero
562 some PP that are relevant in terms of the environmental risk assessment. Some of them
563 due to the great demand and use, such as codeine (analgesic), flufenamic acid (analgesic),
564 sotolol, and timolol (cardiac condition and hypertension), and others, such as
565 clarithromycin, due to its potential role in worsening the current antimicrobial resistance
566 crisis [55]. Similarly, the FWBB treatment showed great effectivity in the long term by
567 removing acridine in 21 days.

568 It is important to highlight that although there were no differences in the total PP
569 removal rate between FWB and FWBB, it is necessary to consider the extra inputs needed
570 to create the biofilm (we need to consider the specialized staff's working hours, the extra
571 facilities such as temperature-controlled chamber and the energy in terms of electricity
572 for create and maintain the biofilm growth conditions). These disadvantages allow us to
573 discriminate in favour of the use of the NBS based in the floating wetlands enhanced with
574 biochar without biofilm, at least under the conditions used in this study. In addition,

575 although out of this study's aim, a long-term treatment performance needs to be
576 considered in future research lines to provide an integrated cost-benefit NBS assessment.

577 Regarding NBS and pharmaceutical pollution removal, several research gaps to be
578 addressed have been claimed, including the ecotoxicity evaluation of NBSs' effluents
579 [56]. The ecotoxicological approach considered in this study has several advantages
580 confronting the chemical assessment. First of all, we have confirmed the lethal effect of
581 the WWTP effluent as a cocktail of contaminants. We cannot give any responsibility to a
582 specific PP but to the toxic mixture. If the WWTP effluent can affect zooplankton
583 organisms to the extent of 20% of the population, that means great environmental impact
584 at that specific point. Although the natural dilution process should always be present, in
585 areas where the streams and rivers' flow decrease largely in summer (seasonally), as in
586 the Mediterranean region [45,57,58], special actions should be taken to reduce PP
587 concentrations in WWTP effluents as a point-source of pollution. The NBS, as the ones
588 we proposed, would be an option to reduce the environmental risk of WWTP effluent due
589 to PP. The changes and variability in rainfall predicted by the Climate Change projections
590 will affect surface water flows and will increase pollutant concentrations, reducing water
591 quality [59].

592 In addition, the toxicological assessment using a behavioural biomarker, such as
593 avoidance behaviour, informs about the organisms' reaction to the toxic cocktail, and,
594 therefore, gives additional and ecologically relevant information. Chemical cues are used
595 by aquatic organisms in several ways, such as to search for food or avoid predators, but
596 most of them to select optimal habitats [60]. WWTP effluents will create areas that the
597 organism will try to avoid (depending on the organism's capacity to move or to escape),
598 which can lead to specific habitat selection and, therefore, uneven organisms' spatial
599 distribution [61,62]. Besides, these direct effects of pharmaceuticals on the traits and
600 abundance of one species can cascade through a community, indirectly affecting other
601 species [6]. In our case, we have confirmed that zooplankton organisms are avoiding those
602 compartments with wastewater, while if the wastewater passes through the NBS (in our
603 case, FWB), the mentioned behaviour does not occur. That means that the NBS reduces
604 the negative effect of wastewater, likely PP polluted, on aquatic ecosystems. This kind of
605 bioassays are even more relevant considering that many transformation products are not
606 included in standard chemical analyses and, sometimes, they are more toxic than the
607 parent product [56]. The ecotoxicological assessment shows the environmental risk
608 reduction when NBSs are implemented and informs about their efficiency. Moreover,

609 behaviour is considered a non-destructive biomarker that can be used as an early warning
610 signal before major environmental impacts occur [63].

611 Although the present study has some limitations (such as the use of static systems
612 microcosms and testing the effects just on one type of zooplankton organism) we provided
613 scientific evidence on the NBS efficiency in PP pollution removal. Furthermore, the
614 efficiency has been confirmed not only with the chemical approach but also with the
615 toxicological approach, presenting the biological repercussions beyond the concentration
616 data. With this ecotoxicological approach, we also highlight the relevance of considering
617 the toxic cocktail, as a whole, in risk assessment. As cost-effective systems, they are also
618 feasible solutions for regions with limited financial resources [64]. For more severe cases,
619 with highly toxic pollutants, NBS can help through the implementation of hybrid systems,
620 e.g. floating wetlands working in conjunction with subsurface systems and sand filtration
621 systems, which will improve the final quality of the treated water [65].

622

623 **5. Conclusion**

624 The proposed nature-based solutions were efficient in reducing PP concentration from
625 wastewater (over 40% removal rate) and reducing its negative effects, as a toxic
626 “cocktail” on aquatic organisms. The results presented in this study give scientific
627 evidence on the usefulness of the proposed NBSs as quaternary treatments and their likely
628 role in solving global water-related environmental problems concerning micropollutants.
629 The best performance was obtained with the floating wetlands enhanced with biochar
630 within a lapse consistent with standard hydraulic retention times (Fig. 3).
631 Bioaugmentation with the microorganisms used in this study did not improve the global
632 efficiency in reducing pharmaceuticals pollution, at least under our conditions. It is
633 crucial to consider the improvement of the wastewater treatment plants’ sustainability
634 with quaternary treatments funded by NBS. Further research must be undertaken to
635 increase NBSs’ efficiency, reduce costs, and break down technical and political barriers
636 to improve their implementation.

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651

652 **CRedit authorship contribution statement**

653 **María Rodríguez-Santamarina** Investigation, Data curation, Writing original draft;
654 **Bienvenida Gilbert López**; Data curation, Writing – review & editing. **Ana Belén**
655 **Martínez-Piernas**; Investigation, Data curation, Writing – review & editing. **Antonio**
656 **Jesús Muñoz-Cobo**, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – review & editing. **M^a**
657 **Eugenia López Valcárcel**: Investigation, Data curation, Formal analysis, Writing –
658 review & editing. **Raquel Jimenez-Melero**: Data curation, Formal analysis, Writing –
659 review & editing. **Gema Parra**: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Project
660 administration, Resources, Supervision, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing –
661 review & editing.

662

663 **Declaration of competing interest**

664 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
665 relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

666

667 **Data availability**

668 **Data will be made available on request and, partially at the institutional repository of**
669 **scientific production of the University of Jaén (RUJA).**

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673 **References.**

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920 Highlights:

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922 - Floating wetlands enhanced with biochar were proposed as Nature Based

923 Solutions (NBSs)

924 - Proposed NBSs were efficient in removing pharmaceuticals at the microcosm scale

925 - NBS efficiency was assessed under chemical and ecotoxicological approaches.

926 - Selected NBS reduces wastewater toxic effects under standard hydraulic retention times

FIGURES AND CAPTIONS

Fig. 1. Avoidance behavior experiments schemes in HemHAS system. a) Dilution gradient using 100% *D. magna* culture water (EMW); 50% wastewater from the treatment plant (WW) + 50% EMW and 100% WW. b) Dilution gradient using 100% EMW, 50% water from the FWB microcosm (FWB) + 50% EMW and 100% FWB.

Fig.3. Total pharmaceutical products (PP) removal rate (%) in wastewater after 7 days in the microcosms treatments: NULL: microcosms without floating wetland; FW: microcosms with floating wetland; FWB: microcosms with floating wetland, improved with biochar; FWBB: microcosms with floating wetland, improved with biofilm coated biochar. Different letters denote significant differences.

Fig. 4. Non-metric multi-dimensional scaling (nMDS) ordination plot based on the Bray-Curtis similarities. Blue triangles Null (microcosms without floating wetland), red triangle FW (microcosms with floating wetland), green square FWB (microcosms with floating wetland with biochar) and pink diamond FWBB (microcosms with floating wetland with biofilm coated microorganism). Numbers above triangles, squares and diamonds represent the sampling days (day 0, 3 and 7).

Fig. 5. Acute toxicity test results showing alive *D. magna* individuals in vessels after exposure for 48h in wastewater (WW) dilutions. Control: 100% *D. magna* culture water. Asterisk (*) means significant differences with control vessels.

Fig. 6. Avoidance behaviour tests. Mean *D. magna* individuals in HeMHAS compartments after 24 h exposure, a) using waste water from the treatment plant (WW) and b) using water from the floating wetland with biochar microcosms (FWB). Asterisk (*) means significant differences with control compartments (Control: 100% *D. magna* culture water).

a)

b)

TABLES

Table 1. Average dissimilarity percentage between treatments and exposure days estimated with a Similarity Percentage Analyses (SIMPER) based on the Bray-Curtis similarities.

	WW Day 0	Null-D3	Null-D7	FW-D3	FW- D7	FWB- D3	FWB-D7	FWBB- D3	FWBB-D7
WW Day 0									
Null-D3	9.6								
Null-D7	16.19	10.58							
FW-D3	12.93	6.71	15.44						
FW-D7	23.32	15.62	11.93	13.09					
FWB-D3	22.22	16.06	16.68	11.99	11.88				
FWB-D7	31.46	23.92	21.35	20.12	11.94	10.83			
FWBB-D3	21.91	14.89	15.88	10.73	10.34	8.41	13		
FWBB-D7	25.37	17.65	15.24	13.72	7.87	9.12	8.02	7.1	

Note: Microcosms treatments: **WW** waste water; **Null**: microcosms without floating wetland, with wastewater; **FW**: microcosms with floating wetland with wastewater; **FWB**: microcosms with floating wetland with wastewater, improved with biochar; **FWBB**: microcosms with floating wetland with wastewater, improved with biofilm coated biochar. D3, sampling day 3. D7, sampling day 7.

Table 2. SIMPER analysis results showing the discriminant pharmaceutical products (PP) between the WW day 0 and a) Null-D7, b) FW-D7, c) FWB-D7 and d) FWBB-D7. Columns 3 and 4: average concentration (fourth square transformed) in the pair compared. Column 5: mean dissimilarity of each PP. Column 6: the ratio of the average contribution (column 5) divided by the standard deviation (SD) of those contributions across the pair of treatments making up this average. Column 7: contribution of each PP to the total dissimilarity in the pair being compared. Column 8: cumulated percentages from column 7.

Pair of groups	PP	Aver. concen. 1	Aver. concen. 2	Diss	Diss/SD	Contrib %	Cum. %
a) WW vs. Null D7	<i>Irbesartan</i>	33.96	0.00	3.47	90.46	21.43	21.43
	<i>Ketoprofen</i>	24.33	0.00	2.49	26.62	15.36	36.79
	<i>Diclofenac</i>	26.77	9.93	1.72	22.26	10.63	47.41
	<i>Eprosartan</i>	25.94	10.89	1.54	12.75	9.50	56.91
	<i>Metformin</i>	20.00	13.66	0.65	8.53	4.01	60.92
	<i>Flufenamic acid</i>	9.93	4.81	0.52	4.44	3.23	64.15
	<i>Gemfibrozil</i>	32.68	37.79	0.52	14.77	3.23	67.38
	<i>Cocaine</i>	4.84	0.00	0.49	18.48	3.05	70.43
b) WW vs. FW-D7	<i>Irbesartan</i>	33.96	0.00	3.78	37.96	16.19	16.19
	<i>Ketoprofen</i>	24.33	0.00	2.71	23.07	11.60	27.80
	<i>Eprosartan</i>	25.94	9.22	1.86	8.78	7.98	35.78
	<i>Diclofenac</i>	26.77	14.87	1.32	4.97	5.67	41.45
	<i>Diphenhydramine</i>	9.96	0.00	1.11	31.45	4.75	46.20
	<i>Metformin</i>	20.00	11.41	0.95	11.67	4.09	50.29
	<i>Atenolol</i>	19.48	11.14	0.93	2.46	4.00	54.29
	<i>Clarithromycin</i>	10.80	3.47	0.82	1.36	3.53	57.83
	<i>Flufenamic acid</i>	9.93	2.64	0.82	1.70	3.50	61.33
	<i>Tramadol</i>	44.81	37.55	0.81	1.83	3.47	64.79
	<i>Sulpiride CRS</i>	31.46	24.81	0.74	6.96	3.18	67.97
<i>Venlafaxine</i>	14.05	8.79	0.59	7.79	2.51	70.48	
c) WW vs. FWB-D7	<i>Irbesartan</i>	33.96	0.00	4.04	96.94	12.85	12.85
	<i>Ketoprofen</i>	24.33	0.00	2.90	27.60	9.21	22.06
	<i>Eprosartan</i>	25.94	10.31	1.86	10.36	5.91	27.97
	<i>Codeine</i>	15.26	0.00	1.82	53.63	5.77	33.74
	<i>Clarithromycin</i>	10.80	0.00	1.29	34.48	4.09	37.83
	<i>Diclofenac</i>	26.77	16.66	1.20	7.22	3.83	41.65
	<i>Sulpiride CRS</i>	31.46	21.43	1.19	5.97	3.80	45.45
	<i>Diphenhydramine</i>	9.96	0.00	1.19	47.83	3.77	49.22
	<i>Tramadol</i>	44.81	34.84	1.18	2.69	3.77	52.98
	<i>Flufenamic acid</i>	9.93	0.00	1.18	9.37	3.76	56.74
	<i>Flecainide</i>	20.72	10.88	1.17	8.19	3.72	60.46
	<i>Metformin</i>	20.00	10.67	1.11	15.06	3.53	63.99
	<i>Atenolol</i>	19.48	10.91	1.02	11.80	3.24	67.23
<i>Sulfamethoxazole</i>	15.13	7.37	0.92	5.10	2.94	70.17	
d) WW vs. FWBB-D7	<i>Irbesartan</i>	33.96	0.00	3.85	101.18	15.19	15.19
	<i>Ketoprofen</i>	24.33	0.00	2.76	27.86	10.88	26.07
	<i>Eprosartan</i>	25.94	10.44	1.76	13.14	6.93	33.00
	<i>Clarithromycin</i>	10.80	0.00	1.23	34.52	4.83	37.83
	<i>Diclofenac</i>	26.77	16.28	1.19	9.34	4.69	42.52
	<i>Tramadol</i>	44.81	34.82	1.13	2.68	4.46	46.98
	<i>Diphenhydramine</i>	9.96	0.00	1.13	48.89	4.45	51.44
	<i>Flecainide</i>	20.72	11.15	1.08	11.71	4.28	55.71
	<i>Metformin</i>	20.00	10.68	1.06	21.13	4.17	59.88
	<i>Sulpiride CRS</i>	31.46	22.34	1.03	7.52	4.08	63.96
	<i>Atenolol</i>	19.48	13.13	0.72	7.54	2.84	66.81
	<i>O-desmethylvenlafaxine</i>	36.47	30.41	0.69	7.80	2.71	69.52
	<i>Venlafaxine</i>	14.05	8.57	0.62	8.27	2.45	71.97

Note: **WW:** wastewater from the treatment plant effluent; **Null:** microcosms without floating wetland, with wastewater; **FW:** microcosms with floating wetland with wastewater; **FWB:** microcosms with floating wetland with wastewater, improved with biochar; **FWBB:** microcosms with floating wetland with wastewater, improved with biofilm coated biochar. D3, sampling day 3. D7, sampling day 7.

Table 3. Results of SIMPER analysis showing the discriminant pharmaceutical products (PP) between pair of groups with the different treatments (Null, FW, FWB, FWBB) on **day 7**. Column 1: pairs being compared. Column 2: PP. Columns 3 and 4: average concentration (fourth square transformed) in both groups of the pair being compared. Column 5: mean dissimilarity of each PP. Column 6: the ratio of the average contribution (column 5) divided by the standard deviation (SD) of those contributions across the pair of treatments making up this average. Column 7: contribution of each PP to the total dissimilarity in the pair being compared. Column 8: cumulated percentages from column 7.

Pair of groups	PP	Aver. concen. 1 group	Aver. concen. 2 group	Diss	Diss/SD	Contrib %	Cum. %
a) Null D7 vs. FW-D7	<i>Diphenhydramine</i>	8.75	0.00	1.13	29.65	9.44	9.44
	<i>Atenolol</i>	18.41	11.14	0.94	2.08	7.90	17.34
	<i>Clarithromycin</i>	10.38	3.47	0.90	1.29	7.56	24.90
	<i>Sulfamethoxazole</i>	16.27	10.46	0.75	4.38	6.29	31.19
	<i>Sulpiride CRS</i>	30.50	24.81	0.73	6.29	6.15	37.35
	<i>Diclofenac</i>	9.93	14.87	0.64	2.09	5.33	42.67
	<i>Telmisartan</i>	17.64	12.76	0.63	3.46	5.29	47.96
	<i>Tramadol</i>	41.79	37.55	0.55	2.60	4.60	52.56
	<i>Flufenamic acid</i>	4.81	2.64	0.55	4.37	4.60	57.16
	<i>Venlafaxine</i>	13.01	8.79	0.54	4.78	4.56	61.72
	<i>O-desmethylvenlafaxine</i>	37.59	33.52	0.53	2.37	4.40	66.12
	<i>Morphine</i>	3.26	0.00	0.42	6.28	3.51	69.63
<i>Flecainide</i>	19.64	16.95	0.35	2.24	2.93	72.56	
b) Null D7 vs. FWB-D7	<i>Codeine</i>	10.56	0.00	1.47	60.60	6.89	6.89
	<i>Clarithromycin</i>	10.38	0.00	1.44	96.92	6.77	13.65
	<i>Sulpiride CRS</i>	30.50	21.43	1.26	5.48	5.92	19.57
	<i>Sulfamethoxazole</i>	16.27	7.37	1.24	7.10	5.81	25.38
	<i>Lamotrigine</i>	36.68	27.90	1.22	11.53	5.73	31.11
	<i>Flecainide</i>	19.64	10.88	1.22	8.66	5.71	36.81
	<i>Diphenhydramine</i>	8.75	0.00	1.22	51.85	5.70	42.52
	<i>O-desmethylvenlafaxine</i>	37.59	29.40	1.14	6.60	5.34	47.85
	<i>Atenolol</i>	18.41	10.91	1.04	6.58	4.88	52.74
	<i>Tramadol</i>	41.79	34.84	0.97	7.66	4.53	57.27
	<i>Diclofenac</i>	9.93	16.66	0.94	4.79	4.39	61.65
	<i>Trimethoprim</i>	10.39	3.94	0.90	16.53	4.20	65.86
<i>Venlafaxine</i>	13.01	6.74	0.87	3.69	4.09	69.95	
<i>Telmisartan</i>	17.64	11.78	0.82	6.08	3.82	73.77	
c) Null D7 vs. FWBB-D7	<i>Clarithromycin</i>	10.38	0.00	1.37	108.90	8.96	8.96
	<i>Diphenhydramine</i>	8.75	0.00	1.15	54.01	7.56	16.52
	<i>Flecainide</i>	19.64	11.15	1.12	16.99	7.33	23.85
	<i>Sulpiride CRS</i>	30.50	22.34	1.07	6.97	7.05	30.90
	<i>Lamotrigine</i>	36.68	28.88	1.03	5.57	6.74	37.64
	<i>O-desmethylvenlafaxine</i>	37.59	30.41	0.94	5.23	6.20	43.84
	<i>Tramadol</i>	41.79	34.82	0.92	7.25	6.02	49.86
	<i>Sulfamethoxazole</i>	16.27	9.78	0.85	8.12	5.61	55.47
	<i>Diclofenac</i>	9.93	16.28	0.84	6.70	5.48	60.95
	<i>Trimethoprim</i>	10.39	5.05	0.70	8.21	4.62	65.57
<i>Atenolol</i>	18.41	13.13	0.69	4.29	4.56	70.13	
d) FW-D7 vs. FWB-D7	<i>Codeine</i>	11.02	0.00	1.72	33.10	14.44	14.44
	<i>Lamotrigine</i>	34.16	27.90	0.98	7.21	8.18	22.63
	<i>Flecainide</i>	16.95	10.88	0.94	4.82	7.90	30.53
	<i>O-desmethylvenlafaxine</i>	33.52	29.40	0.64	3.64	5.37	35.90
	<i>Trimethoprim</i>	7.76	3.94	0.60	12.16	4.99	40.88
	<i>Sulpiride CRS</i>	24.81	21.43	0.53	1.97	4.41	45.30
<i>Clarithromycin</i>	3.47	0.00	0.53	0.67	4.41	49.71	

	<i>Sulfamethoxazole</i>	10.46	7.37	0.48	2.16	4.02	53.73
	<i>9(10H)-Acridone</i>	2.95	0.00	0.46	22.17	3.86	57.59
	<i>Atenolol</i>	11.14	10.91	0.42	1.94	3.55	61.14
	<i>Tramadol</i>	37.55	34.84	0.42	2.00	3.51	64.64
	<i>Diclofenac</i>	14.87	16.66	0.40	1.60	3.39	68.03
	<i>Flufenamic acid</i>	2.64	0.00	0.40	0.67	3.36	71.40
e)	<i>Flecainide</i>	16.95	11.15	0.85	6.25	10.76	10.76
	<i>Lamotrigine</i>	34.16	28.88	0.77	3.62	9.83	20.59
	<i>Flufenamic acid</i>	2.64	7.00	0.75	1.61	9.56	30.15
	<i>Morphine</i>	0.00	3.44	0.51	11.19	6.42	36.57
	<i>Clarithromycin</i>	3.47	0.00	0.50	0.67	6.29	42.86
	<i>O-desmethylvenlafaxine</i>	33.52	30.41	0.45	2.39	5.77	48.63
	<i>Atenolol</i>	11.14	13.13	0.40	1.02	5.07	53.70
	<i>Trimethoprim</i>	7.76	5.05	0.40	4.60	5.05	58.75
	<i>Tramadol</i>	37.55	34.82	0.40	1.96	5.03	63.78
	<i>Sulpiride CRS</i>	24.81	22.34	0.36	1.85	4.58	68.36
	<i>Diclofenac</i>	14.87	16.28	0.34	1.67	4.31	72.66
f)	<i>Codeine</i>	0.00	10.93	1.76	67.12	21.93	21.93
	<i>Flufenamic acid</i>	0.00	7.00	1.13	5.88	14.04	35.98
	<i>Sotalol</i>	0.00	2.80	0.45	38.84	5.63	41.60
	<i>Timolol</i>	0.00	2.70	0.44	11.05	5.42	47.03
	<i>9(10H)-Acridone</i>	0.00	2.64	0.43	16.28	5.30	52.33
	<i>Sulfamethoxazole</i>	7.37	9.78	0.39	2.03	4.85	57.18
	<i>Atenolol</i>	10.91	13.13	0.36	2.28	4.44	61.61
	<i>Venlafaxine</i>	6.74	8.57	0.30	1.12	3.70	65.31
	<i>Sulpiride CRS</i>	21.43	22.34	0.26	1.21	3.21	68.52
	<i>Carbamazepine 10-11-Epoxide</i>	5.23	6.82	0.26	2.15	3.20	71.73

Note: Microcosms treatments: **Null:** microcosms without floating wetland, with wastewater; **FW:** microcosms with floating wetland with wastewater; **FWB:** microcosms with floating wetland with wastewater, improved with biochar; **FWBB:** microcosms with floating wetland with wastewater, improved with biofilm coated biochar. D7, sampling day 7.

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Supplementary Material

Supplementary material 04022025.docx

